

**CREATING A QUASI-FEDERAL JUDICIAL SYSTEM
OF THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITIES**

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Am.J.Comp.L.	American Journal of Comparative Law
BVerfG	Bundesverfassungsgericht
BVerfGE	Entscheidungen des Bundesverfassungsgerichts
C.M.L.R.	Common Market Law Reports
C.M.L.Rev.	Common Market Law Review
Col. J.E.L.	Columbia Journal of European Law
EC	European Communities
ECR	European Court Reports
E.L.J.	European Law Journal
E.L.Rev.	European Law Review
Env.L.R.	Environmental Law Reports
E.P.L.	European Public Law
EU	European Union
Harv. Int'l. L.J.	Harvard International Law Journal
I.C.L.Q.	International and Comparative Law Quarterly
L.Q.R.	Law Quarterly Review
OJ	Official Journal of the European Union
Tex. Int'l L.J.	Texas International Law Journal
YB.E.L.	Yearbook of European Law
W.L.R.	Weekly Law Reports

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INTRODUCTION

This paper will focus on an ever-green topic of Community law – the judicial system of the European Communities. The term “Community judicial system” encompasses not only the Court of Justice of the European Communities,¹ but also the system’s indispensable components: the national courts.² The need for reform of the Community judicial system has attracted attention of many scholars. Some of them have attempted to propose a new structure of Community courts, which according to some opinions have become ineffective in their primary purpose – the protection of the Rule of Law within the Community and its Member States. Most of the scholars have focused on either the preliminary ruling procedure,³ particularly as regards its length and the Court’s gradually growing incapability to deal with its case-load therein, and/or on individuals’ standing in the direct action procedure.⁴

The Community and the Member States themselves have also felt the need for a reform of the Community judicial system. Working papers were presented by the Court⁵ as well as by a group of experts set up by the Commission⁶ to consider necessary changes before the Nice IGC in 2000. However, the IGC failed to adopt any substantial changes and regrettably the same applies for the Convention on Future of Europe which submitted the Draft Treaty Establishing a Constitution for Europe last year.⁷

The purpose of this paper differs from proposing a new design of the Community judiciary. The argument will be that the Court has already been gradually creating a ‘Quasi-federal Judicial System of the Communities’ (hereinafter “the System“),⁸ remedying the missing will of the

¹ Hereinafter referred to as “the Court” or the “Court of Justice”. If not otherwise indicated, only the European Court of Justice is meant.

² Cf. *Craig P.* The Jurisdiction of the Community Courts Reconsidered. in: *de Búrca G. Weiler J.H.H. (eds.)* The European Court of Justice. Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2001, 177-214 at p.178: “It is clear that properly understood we have three types of Community Court, not just two: the ECJ, the CFI, and national courts.”

³ Art. 234 EC.

⁴ Art. 230 EC, second paragraph.

⁵ *The Future of the Judicial System of the European Union*, accessible on the web-site of the Court: <http://curia.eu.int/en/txts/intergov/index.htm> (13.4.2004).

⁶ *Report by the Working Party on the Future of the European Communities’ Court System*, accessible on the web-site of the Commission http://europa.eu.int/comm/dgs/legal_service/docs/du_e_en.pdf (13.4. 2004).

⁷ CONV 850/03, accessible at http://european-convention.eu.int/docs/Treaty/cv00850_en03.pdf (11.1. 2004).

⁸ I attempted to avoid a word “federal”, being aware about still remaining structural differences between the EU and a genuine federation. However, “[a]lthough the word ‘federalism’ continues to stir rancor among some political

Member States to adopt necessary changes by amending the Treaties. The System does not resolve problems with the case-load of the Court, but it seeks for better unity and coherence within the Community legal order. The System allows individuals to “appeal” national courts’ decisions by way of preliminary references from national courts, which hear actions on liability of a Member State for a breach committed by its judiciary. It further gives the Court’s case-law binding force upon the national courts. Three recent judgements of the Court – *Köbler*,⁹ *Kühne & Heitz*¹⁰ and *Commission v. Italy*¹¹ - show how the Court crowned its creative efforts towards the System and balanced some kind of hierarchy with the cooperative relationship, which the Court still needs with its national counterparts.

The need for the System is not contestable, if one accepts the unity and coherence of the Community legal order to be a legitimate aim for the Court to pursue.¹² The paper will base its argumentation on acceptance of this aim, even though it is not to say that the opposite view is impossible. It is believed however, that the Court, aiming at protection of the Rule of Law within the Community, is only trying to reconcile the irreconcilable: to promote uniform law within the disunited structure of the Community judicature, which if understood literally, does not allow for direct control over the “inferior” parts. Thus, the System itself cannot remedy the weaknesses of the Community legal order and the paper will show some problems, which will be hardly overcome in the prospective functioning of the System.

The first part of the paper will present the Founding Judgements. In *Köbler* the Court confirmed that the principle of Member State liability for breaches of Community law also applies when a breach is attributable to national courts. The case will be discussed in detail, since it well illustrates how the Court reasoned when creating the System and how it tried to overcome the Member States’ resistance against it. *Köbler* should be read in connection with other two cases

leaders of EU Member States, its use as a working description of the relationship between the judicial processes of the EU and its Member States has gained wide acceptance among Community lawyers.” *Dubinsky P.R.* The Essential Function of Federal Courts: The European Union and the United States Compared. [1994] 42 Am.J.Comp.L. 295 at pp. 340-341.

⁹ Case C-224/01 *Gerhard Köbler v. Republik Österreich* [2003] 30.9. 2003, not yet reported.

¹⁰ Case C-453/00 *Kühne & Heitz NV v. Produktschap voor Pluimvee en Eieren* [2004] 13.1. 2004, not yet reported.

¹¹ Case C-129/00 *Commission of the European Communities v. Italian Republic* [2003] 9.12. 2003, not yet reported.

¹² See an analysis of the legal reasoning of the Court rooted in the particular character of the Community legal order: *Bengoetxea J., MacCormick N., Soriano L.M.* Integration and Integrity in the Legal Reasoning of the European Court of Justice. In: de Búrca, Weiler 2001, 43-85 at pp. 43-48 and 82-85.

decided by the Court approximately at the same time: *Commission v. Italy*¹³ and *Kühne&Heitz NV*.¹⁴ This interrelation was amongst others indicated by advocates general in the cases.¹⁵ *Kühne & Heitz NV* represents another way in which the Court seeks to control the correct application of Community law by national courts. In certain circumstances the Court allowed the re-opening of final administrative decisions given by national authorities in breach of Community law, if the decision was confirmed by a court failing to refer a preliminary question. Finally in *Commission v. Italy* had the very first opportunity to decide an infringement procedure initiated by the Commission against a Member State since its courts (and administrative authorities) were constantly applying certain tax legislation in breach of Community law.

The description of the Quasi-federal Judicial System itself forms the second part of the paper. It starts by showing how the System was founded. It is based on reading the Founding Judgements in their mutual context. *Kühne & Heitz NV* in connection with *Köbler* established an appellate procedure *sui generis*, allowing individuals to claim their Community rights in national courts more effectively, since they have much better probability that their claim (in a form of a preliminary question) will reach the Court of Justice. This at the same time gave the Court another means to say its last word in Community law disputes and to enhance the unity of the Community legal order. The Court further strengthened its position within the System by making its case-law binding on national courts. This will be described on the background of the study, which at that time denied such a possibility.¹⁶ At the same time, the Court was well aware about the price it must have paid for creating the System and it tried to depress the costs to the minimum. The cooperative relationship with the national courts was at stake. However, *Köbler* together with *Commission v. Italy* show that by its prudent reasoning the Court preserved the relationship, having the possibility to re-define it in the future.

¹³ *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 11.

¹⁴ *Kühne & Heitz NV*, *supra* note 10.

¹⁵ See opinion of AG Léger in Case C-224/01 *Köbler* [2003] 8.4. 2003, not yet reported, para. 10, opinion of AG Geelhoed in Case C-129/00 *Commission v. Italy* [2003] 3.6. 2003, not yet reported, para. 3. In his opinion in Case C-453/00 *Kühne & Heitz NV*, [2003] 17.6. 2003, not yet reported, AG Léger referred to *Köbler* when addressing points common to both cases – paras. 46 and 66 of his opinion therein.

¹⁶ *Toth A.G.* The Authority of Judgements of the European Court of Justice: Binding Force and Legal Effects. [1984] 4 YB. E.L. 1.

The third part of the paper will present shortcomings and problems of the System. The first of them is the Court's reasoning in the Founding Cases, which may problematize acceptance of the System by its constituent parts – the national courts. In order to avoid some irresolvable difficulties posed by liability of a State for judicial breaches (as a fundamental component of the System), it simply did not respond some of the referring courts' questions, which may cause difficulties when implementing the System. Another deficiency lies in the contradiction of the System's constitutional *base* – the protection of individuals – and its *real purpose* – unity of the Community legal order. The System's base is not an exemption amongst the Court's constitutional doctrines: protection of individuals within the Community lies behind e.g. the doctrine of direct effect¹⁷ or, of course, the respect for human rights.¹⁸ Nevertheless, the practical consequences of the created System may not actually enhance the judicial protection of individuals due to procedural constraints, mainly the length of the whole procedure aiming at protection of individual's rights. The System however instead primarily aims at perfecting the Community legal order. The protection of individuals is not a final purpose but a way how to achieve it. Still, the inherent weakness of the System, i.e. a danger of unmanageable case-load of the Court, which is already now seen as the most serious problem of the Court, may compromise the very functioning of the System, since individuals would not be motivated to use the tracks of an “appeal” to protect their rights, since this track is lengthy and costly. The Court has missed the opportunity to reformulate its relationship to national courts giving them more responsibility for interpretation and application of Community law.

The conclusion submits that the Court did not have however another possibility if it wanted to promote coherency and unity of the Community legal order. Therefore, regardless the weaknesses, the System should be accepted.

¹⁷ Case 26/62 *NV Algemene Transport- en Expeditie Onderneming van Gend & Loos v. Netherlands Inland Revenue Administration* [1963] ECR 1 at p. 12.

¹⁸ For a recent example see Case C-112/00 *Eugen Schmidberger, Internationale Transporte und Planzüge v. Republik Österreich* [2003] ECR I-5659, paras. 71-74.

1 THE FOUNDING JUDGEMENTS – AN OVERVIEW

1.1 Prelude – the Problem of the Disobedient Court¹⁹

Courts are the key actors for the correct application of Community law in Member States. Even though the judges should be trained to apply the law correctly, they may make mistakes like other public authorities. That they sometimes disregard Community law intentionally is a different problem. The Commission's annual reports on monitoring the application of Community law mention judgements of national courts which, according to its opinion, breached Community law. These breaches may lie in incorrect interpretation and subsequent application of substantive provisions of Community law or in a breach of the duty imposed upon national courts by Art. 234 EC to refer certain questions of Community law to the Court of Justice.²⁰ It is hard to make a sharp distinction between these two kinds of breaches since they are closely interrelated and a breach of a substantive provision may result from the fact that the national court failed to pose the preliminary question.

Probably the most famous example is the case *Cohn-Bendit* decided by the French Council of State (*Conseil d'Etat*) in 1978²¹ which denied the existence of a principle formulated by the Court of Justice – direct effect of directives.

The well-known student leader Daniel Cohn-Bendit, a German citizen, was served with a deportation order issued by the French Minister of Interior after student disturbances in Paris in May 1968. Cohn-Bendit requested the cancellation of the order in 1975 on the ground that the social and political climate in France had substantially changed. The Minister of Interior had rejected his application, against which Cohn-Bendit appealed to the Administrative Tribunal in Paris (*Tribunal Administratif de Paris*), arguing that the decision abused the limits of discretion

¹⁹ The title refers to an analysis of the Francovich jurisprudence by Carol Harlow: *Francovich and the Problem of the Disobedient State*. [1996] 2 E.L.J. 199.

²⁰ For an overview of national supreme courts practice failing to refer preliminary questions correctly see *infra* pp. 49-50.

²¹ *Minister of the Interior v. Cohn-Bendit* [1980] 1 C.M.L.R. 543. *Oppenheimer A. The Relationship between European Community Law and National Law: the Cases*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1994, pp. 317-334.

and disregarded Directive 64/221/EEC, which regulated that field.²² The *Tribunal* stayed the proceedings and referred to the Court of Justice questions regarding application of the directive. However, the Minister appealed this referral to the *Conseil d'Etat* arguing that the directive was inapplicable to the case, since it cannot be applied directly. The opinion of the *Commissaire du Gouvernement* recommended the *Conseil d'Etat's* referring a preliminary question to the Court of Justice to allow the Court changing its jurisprudence, which gave the direct effect to directives. The *Conseil d'Etat* nevertheless decided to not do so and ruled that directives are not capable of having direct effect. It finally allowed the Minister's appeal – in the end, the case was not referred to the Court of Justice by the *Tribunal* either.

Of course, this judgement met with very strong criticism.²³ As the *Commissaire du Gouvernement* herself stated, “[a]t the level of the European Community there should not be either rule by judges nor war between judges. There should be place there for dialogue between judges”.²⁴ However, by that time it seemed that there was neither remedy for Cohn-Bendit or another individual to defend his Community rights effectively nor a means for the Court of Justice to enforce national courts' posing a preliminary question and to abide by the Court's case-law. The discordance within the Community legal order remained without any chance for its remedying by neither the Court nor another Community institution.²⁵

Almost twenty years later, professor Köbler in Austria found himself in a similar situation. However, his chances were quite different from those of Cohn-Bendit, as we will see in the following section. It was exactly his case which laid the foundations of the ‘Quasi-federal Judicial System’.

²² Council Directive 64/221/EEC of 25 February 1964 on the coordination of special measures concerning the movement and residence of foreign nationals which are justified on grounds of public policy, public security or public health, OJ 1964 P 56/850.

²³ See e.g. the Case Note by *P.J.G. Kapteyn*, [1979] 16 C.M.L.Rev. 701 or *Bebr G.* The Rambling Ghost of “Cohn-Bendit”: *Acte Clair* and the Court of Justice. [1983] 20 C.M.L.Rev. 439 and a literature referred to in note 5 thereof.

²⁴ Oppenheimer 1994 at p. 332.

²⁵ Cf. inter alia Schermers H.G., Waelbroeck D.F. *Judicial Protection in the European Union. 6th Ed.*, The Hague/London/New York, Kluwer Law International, 2001; at pp. 272-273 and 630-631 or Lenaerts K., Arts D., Bray R. (ed.) *Procedural Law of the European Union*. London, Sweet&Maxwell, 1999, p. 53. Both of them were yet indicating the possibility to claim damages from a Member State. See also *ter Kuile B.H.* To Refer or not to Refer: About the Last Paragraph of Article 177 of the EC Treaty. In: *Curtin D., Heukels T.* Institutional Dynamics of European Integration. Essays in Honour of Henry G. Schermers. Vol. II. Dordrecht/Boston/London, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1994, 381-389.

1.2 The case of professor Köbler – to find a way out from the trap of national judiciary²⁶

In 1996 professor Köbler applied for a special length-of-service increment for university professors in Austria. He did so, even though the requirement of the relevant law was to complete the period at Austrian universities only and he had completed the required 15 years' period as a professor also in Member States other than Austria. However, he claimed that such a requirement led to an indirect discrimination contrary to the Treaty, in particular to the Free Movement of Workers.²⁷ Nevertheless, his application was dismissed by administrative authorities, and his dispute eventually reached the Austrian Supreme Administrative Court (*Verwaltungsgerichtshof*). In the course of the proceedings that court then, referred to the Court of Justice the question as to whether work of equal value which is performed in another Member State (as professor Köbler's work as a university professor outside Austria was) must be taken into account in exactly the same way as such work performed in the Member State applying a salary scheme in which remuneration depends on *inter alia* length of service (i.e. in Austria).²⁸ Since the same issue was dealt with by the Court of Justice in another case, *Schöning-Kougebetopoulou*,²⁹ the Registrar of the Court asked the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* whether it deemed its reference necessary in the light of this judgement. The *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* subsequently informed the parties that the legal issue, which was the subject-matter of the question submitted for a preliminary ruling, seemed to be resolved in favour of the applicant, professor Köbler, and withdrew its referral. However, the story did not have a happy-ending. The *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* changed its characterization of the contested increment and held that it was in fact a special bonus for loyalty (and not a bonus for a length of service). According to the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof's* interpretation of the *Schöning-Kougebetopoulou* judgement, the requirement to complete the whole 15-year-long period of being a university professor only in Austria was justified. Without referring any further questions to the Court of Justice, it finally dismissed professor Köbler's claim to obtain the increment.

²⁶ Case comments may be found in *Breuer M.* State liability for judicial wrongs and Community law: the case of Gerhard Köbler v. Austria. [2004] 29 E.L.Rev. 243 or in [2004] 41 C.M.L.Rev. 813 by C.D. Classen.

²⁷ Article 48 EC and Article 7(1) of Regulation (EEC) No. 1612/68 of the Council of 15 October 1968 on freedom of movement for workers within the Community, [1968] O.J. L 257/2.

²⁸ Case C- 382/97 *Gerhard Köbler v. Bundesminister für Wissenschaft, Forschung und Kunst*, OJ 1998 C 7/9.

²⁹ Case C-15/96 *Kalliope Schöning-Kougebetopoulou v. Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg* [1998] ECR I-47.

The case could very well have ended there, since at that time there did not appear to be any Community remedy against a decision of a national court which disregarded its obligations under the Treaty, as we saw in case of Cohn-Bendit.

The *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III* judgement indicated a possible change in that regard:

[The principle of State liability] holds good for any case in which a Member State breaches Community law, *whatever be the organ of the State whose act or omission was responsible for the breach*. In addition, in view of the fundamental requirement of the Community legal order that Community law be uniformly applied [...] the obligation to make good damage caused to individuals by breaches of Community law *cannot depend on domestic rules as to the division of powers between constitutional authorities*. [...] In international law a State whose liability for breach of an international commitment is in issue will be viewed as a single entity, irrespective of whether the breach which gave rise to the damage is attributable to the legislature, the judiciary or the executive. This must apply a fortiori in the Community legal order [...].³⁰

The fact that also judicial decisions may give rise to Member States' liability was mentioned by Advocate General Léger in *Hedley Lomas*³¹ and discussed by scholars.³² However, opinions contesting such possibility still existed.³³

Professor Köbler became the first to turn the debate into the reality when he claimed damages against Austria in the Regional Civil Court (*Landesgericht für Zivilrechtssachen Wien*). He claimed reparation of the loss which he allegedly suffered as a result of the non-payment to him of a special length-of-service increment. He maintained that the judgement of the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof*, in which it held that a special length-of-service increment does not constitute a loyalty bonus, infringed directly applicable provisions of Community law, as interpreted by the Court of Justice..

³⁰ Joined Cases C-46 and C-48/93 *Brasserie du Pêcheur SA v. Bundesrepublik Deutschland and The Queen v Secretary of State for Transport, ex parte: Factortame Ltd and others* [1996] ECR I-1029, paras. 32-34, emphasis added.

³¹ Opinion of AG Léger in Case C-5/94 *R. v. Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries & Food, ex parte Hedley Lomas* [1996] ECR I-2553, para. 114.

³² *Toner H.* Thinking the Unthinkable? State Liability for Judicial Acts after *Factortame (III)*. [1997] 17 YB.E.L. 165, *Anagnostaras G.* The Principle of State Liability for Judicial Breaches: The Impact of European Community Law. [2001] 7 E.P.L. 281 are probably the most detailed analysis published in English.

³³ E.g. *Steiner J.* Limits of State Liability for Breach of EU Law. [1998] 4 E.P.L. 69 at pp. 91-92.

Hearing the case of liability claim, the *Landesgericht* then referred to the Court of Justice several questions which may be summarized as follows: whether a Member State can be held responsible for an act of its supreme court; if so, the conditions for such liability; and then finally whether such conditions were met in the case of professor Köbler. The last of the questions referred shows the conundrum that is created if Member State liability for decisions made in national judicial systems is recognized. Such responsibility leads to the odd and unprecedented situation where lower-court judges are forced to adjudge the legality of decisions by higher court judges. And paradoxically, it is possible that the claim for damages may end in the same court, which gave the judgement breaching Community law. It is no wonder the *Landesgericht* posed such detailed questions to the Court, leaving the ruling on whether the conditions of liability were fulfilled in case of professor Köbler for this Court as well.

1.2.1 The question of principle

In view of the many arguments presented by the parties to the case, the Commission and intervening Member States,³⁴ it was not easy for the Court to affirm its previous positions regarding the principle of Member State liability. While the Commission and the German and Netherlands Governments accepted the existence of such a liability in the Community legal order, the French and British governments contested it absolutely. Let us discuss some of their arguments to see, how the Court reasoned.

All intervening parties cited the principle of *res judicata* as an argument against imposing liability upon a Member State for a decision of its court given in breach of Community law.³⁵ It is a possible point of view that a claim for damages repeats the original dispute with a changed legal basis, but with an identical merit. The party dissatisfied in the original dispute is “appealing” the final decision by claiming the damages which this decision allegedly caused. The court hearing the damage claim must at the same time in a certain sense review the original decision. Thus, the liability for judicial breaches of Community law may go against the principle of legal certainty and finality of disputes.

³⁴ They were Germany, France, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom.

³⁵ The Commission and the German and Netherlands Governments argued by this principle in order to reason narrower application of liability to judicial acts – see Case C-224/01 *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 16. This principle is also elaborated by the authors mentioned above who wrote about the responsibility of a Member State for judicial acts before Köbler: Toner 1997 at p. 176 and Anagnostaras 2001 at p. 289.

Nevertheless, when deciding whether the liability for judicial acts is possible in Community law, the Court of Justice completely excluded such a conflict. It stated that

[P]roceedings seeking to render the State liable do not have the same purpose and do not necessarily involve the same parties as the proceedings resulting in the decision which has acquired the status of *res judicata*. The applicant in an action to establish the liability of the State will, if successful, secure an order against it for reparation of the damage incurred but not necessarily a declaration invalidating the status of *res judicata* of the judicial decision which was responsible for the damage. In any event, the principle of State liability inherent in the Community legal order requires such reparation, but not revision of the judicial decision which was responsible for the damage.³⁶

As we will see further, the respect for *res judicata* may appear in a very different light when we read *Köbler* together with *Kühne & Heitz*.³⁷ We will discuss this in part 3.1 of the paper.

When the Court dealt with arguments presented by intervening national governments regarding the difficulty of designating a court competent to determine disputes concerning the reparation of damage resulting from decisions of other court, it used the principle of national procedural autonomy to make its work easier. Indeed, it would be a problem when judges of the lowest court have to decide on breaches committed by the highest national judicial instance. In response the Court simply stated that

According to settled case-law, in the absence of Community legislation, it is for the internal legal order of each Member State to designate the competent courts and lay down the detailed procedural rules for legal proceedings intended fully to safeguard the rights which individuals derive from Community law [...]It is not for the Court to become involved in resolving questions of jurisdiction to which the classification of certain legal situations based on Community law may give rise in the national judicial system³⁸

³⁶ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 39. See also opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, [2003] supra note 15, para. 101, which confirms this formal view: “According to the prevailing traditional definition, the legal authority of a judicial decision - and, as a consequence, *res judicata* - is applicable only in certain circumstances, where there is a threefold identity - of subject-matter, legal basis and parties - between a dispute already resolved and a subsequent dispute. [... A dispute] which relates to a claim for reparation of loss or damage caused by a breach of Community law and is brought against the State does not fulfil that requirement of threefold identity (which is cumulative, not alternative)”.

³⁷ See infra section 2.1 at pp. 29-33 and section 3.1 at pp. 43-45.

³⁸ *Köbler* supra note 9, paras. 46, 47, also referring to the Court’s previous “settled case-law” on that matter.

We will see further how different may be uses of the principle of national procedural autonomy. Already at this point we may see that the “guidance” of the Court was of no help to the referring national court.

Nothing thus prevented the Court from reaching the conclusion that, as a matter of principle, there is no distinction when a Member State is to be held liable for an unlawful act stemming from its judiciary. The principle of liability on the part of a Member State is, according to the Court, inherent in the system of the Treaty.³⁹ As in the context of an infringement procedure,⁴⁰ a Member State may be held liable no matter which authority is responsible for the breach.⁴¹ This follows from the principle which views a State as a single entity, which is applied in international law and in view of the Court *a fortiori* must apply in the Community legal order which directly governs the situation of individuals.⁴²

This Court’s conclusion is further strengthened by “the essential role played by the judiciary in the protection of the rights derived by individuals from Community rules”.⁴³

[A] court adjudicating at last instance is by definition the last judicial body before which individuals may assert the rights conferred on them by Community law. Since an infringement of those rights by a final decision of such a court cannot thereafter normally be corrected, individuals cannot be deprived of the possibility of rendering the State liable in order in that way to obtain legal protection of their rights.⁴⁴

As we see, the Court attributes liability only if “a court adjudicating in last instance” infringes Community law. One must ask whether *only* these courts may incur liability on the part of a Member State. This question is particularly interesting if we compare *Köbler* with *Commission v. Italy* discussed further.⁴⁵ In this case Advocate General Geelhoed came to the conclusion that also lower courts may cause an infringement of Community law for which a Member State may be condemned pursuant to the Art. 226 procedure. This is not conclusive, however, since this

³⁹ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 30, referring to further case-law of the Court.

⁴⁰ See discussion infra at p. 26.

⁴¹ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 31.

⁴² *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 32. The Court is summarising its reasoning firstly used in *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III* – see supra note 30.

⁴³ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 33.

⁴⁴ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 34.

⁴⁵ See infra at pp. 28-29.

statement applied in the context of an infringement procedure, which is very different from an action for reparation instituted by an individual. In contrast to the latter, which is based on a single wrongful decision of a national court (like the decision of the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* in *Köbler*), the Commission would start an infringement procedure only in case of some systematic violations of Community law by the national judiciary. According to the Court in *Commission v. Italy*

[...] isolated or numerically insignificant judicial decisions in the context of case-law taking a different direction, or still more a construction disowned by the national supreme court, cannot be taken into account.⁴⁶

Also when discussing the principle of Member State liability Advocate General Léger in *Köbler* focused on supreme courts. He emphasised their “leading role in the application of Community law”⁴⁷ because of “their traditional functions of ensuring that the law is uniformly interpreted”.⁴⁸ In a certain sense, they are responsible for the correct interpretation and application of Community law within the whole national judiciary. Liability of a Member State for their malfunction is therefore even more tenable.

We may thus conclude that in *Köbler* the Court limited the principle of Member States liability only to wrongful acts of their supreme courts. Nevertheless such conclusion may not be definitive, and we may see whether future developments will lead to its modification.⁴⁹

After confirming the existence of the principle of Member States liability for breaches of Community law committed by their supreme courts, the Court analysed the conditions for establishing such liability. Do they differ from those defined by the Court in previous cases which dealt with breaches by national administration or the legislature, or should they be the same, since there is no compelling reason to distinguish the national judiciary from the rest of the system of State authority?

⁴⁶ *Commission v. Italy*, supra note 11, para. 32.

⁴⁷ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, para. 71.

⁴⁸ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, para. 72.

⁴⁹ Another case dealing with Member States liability for judicial breaches is currently pending in the Court: Case C-173/03 *Fallimento ‘raghetti del Mediterraneo’ SPA v. Italian Republic*, OJ 2003 C 158/10. It concerns however also a court of last instance.

1.2.2 Conditions of liability

The Court defined in its previous case-law the test of Member States' liability as threefold:

- the rule of law infringed must be intended to confer rights on individuals;
- the breach must be sufficiently serious;
- and there must be a direct causal link between the breach of the obligation incumbent on the State and the loss or damage sustained by the injured parties.⁵⁰

According to the Court in *Köbler* these conditions apply as well for a case when loss or damage is caused by the decision of a national court adjudicating in last instance.⁵¹ However, in further elaborating the second of the conditions – that the breach must be sufficiently serious, the Court states that liability “can be incurred only in the *exceptional case* where [a court adjudicating in last instance] has manifestly infringed the applicable law”.⁵²

These “exceptional cases” are nevertheless defined by *the same* factors already stipulated by the Court in *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III* when defining “manifest and grave disregard of the limits on the discretion of a Member State or a Community institution” in cases of “ordinary liability”.⁵³ The Court merely added another factor - non-compliance by the court in question with its obligation to make a reference for a preliminary ruling under the third paragraph of Article 234 EC.⁵⁴

Advocate General Léger was of a slightly different opinion. He disagreed on the relevance of two of these factors - the position of the Community institutions and whether the breach of Community law was intentional or involuntary.⁵⁵ As regards the former, he considered that

⁵⁰ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 51, citing Case C-424/97 *Salomone Haim v. Kassenzahnärztliche Vereinigung Nordrhein* [2000] ECR I-5123, para. 36.

⁵¹ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 52.

⁵² *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 53, emphasis added.

⁵³ Cf. *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III* supra note 30, para. 56. The relevant factors therefore are: the degree of clarity and precision of the rule infringed, whether the infringement was intentional, whether the error of law was excusable or inexcusable, the position taken, where applicable, by a Community institution. - *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 55.

⁵⁴ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 55.

⁵⁵ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, para. 154.

conduct by the Commission could qualify as the position of Community institution, cognisance of which is however improbable in the case of a national judiciary. Such an argument seems nevertheless unjustified, since the relevant position may be presented to the national court by the parties to the case.⁵⁶ We may nevertheless view the term “Community institution” as encompassing also the Court itself. Then it is particularly interesting to consider, whether the Court cannot itself contribute to the breach in question, by e.g. giving an unclear interpretation or by declining to give such an interpretation at all.

Peter Wattel, Advocate General of the Netherlands Supreme Court (*Hoge Raad*), makes this point in his recently published upset reaction to *Köbler*.⁵⁷ He cites as example two questions relating to tax law referred to the ECJ by the *Hoge Raad*. Just as the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* in *Köbler*, the *Hoge Raad* was asked whether it deemed it necessary to maintain its questions in light of subsequent ECJ case-law which was soon to be published. Although the *Hoge Raad* withdrew one of the questions, it nevertheless maintained the second one of them. This did not prevent the Court from deciding by an order according to Art. 104(3) of the Rules of Procedure⁵⁸ indicating that “the answer to that question is clear from the case law”.⁵⁹ Wattel submits to the contrary that such an answer by the Court was of very little assistance to the *Hoge Raad* in deciding the case before it and says that “the ECJ sometimes entertains a very optimistic view on the clarity of its case law”.⁶⁰ Of course the national court in question may send a further request for preliminary ruling to clarify the point; however, the preliminary rulings should be seen within the context of national procedures. Each reference entails the prolongation of the whole proceedings,⁶¹ which few judges like. Delays in preliminary rulings are indeed amongst the reasons why some national

⁵⁶ It was even mentioned by a legal adviser who deals with EC law cases on a national level in Sweden that it may be a part of the procedural tactics to make a complaint to the Commission, when a national law or practice is in breach of Community law. The Commission’s position (if available) may then serve as an argument in the case, compelling the national court to consider EC law implication of the case before it. Oral presentation of O. Linden, Stockholm office of Linklaters, Department of Law, Stockholm University, 28.10.2003.

⁵⁷ *Wattel P. Köbler, CILFIT and Welthgrove: We can’t go on meeting like this.* [2004] 41 C.M.L.Rev. 177.

⁵⁸ Rules of Procedure of the Court of Justice of the European Communities of 19 June 1991, OJ 1991 L 176/7.

⁵⁹ Order of the Court in Case C-102/00 *Welthgrove BV v. Staatssecretaris van Financiën* [2001] ECR I-5679.

⁶⁰ Wattel 2004 at p. 183. Wattel mentions another case where the Court did not respond to one of the questions at all – Case C-168/01 *Bosal Holding BV v. Staatssecretaris van Financiën* [2003] 18.9. 2003, not yet reported.

⁶¹ The Court’s annual report from 2003 gives statistics on the duration of proceedings between 1998 and 2003. In the case of preliminary ruling procedures, they currently last approximately two years. Annual Reports of the Court are available at <http://www.curia.eu.int/en/instit/presentationfr/rapport.htm> (11.5. 2004).

judges do not request them.⁶² It may therefore be well that unclear or incomplete responses by the Court may excuse national courts' misapplication of Community law.

For Léger a decisive factor is whether an error of law committed by a national supreme court was excusable or not.⁶³ In his view such error is inexcusable when a supreme court takes a decision which is contrary to provisions of Community law although their scope and meaning are clear.⁶⁴

According to the Advocate General the same applies when the court in question manifestly disregards the Court's case-law. This factor of "sufficiently serious breach" appeared already in *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III*, and the Court itself has repeated it in slightly different words as well in its judgement in *Köbler*:

In any event, an infringement of Community law will be sufficiently serious where the decision [of a national court] concerned was made in manifest breach of the case-law of the Court in the matter.⁶⁵

This factor, which deals with the binding effects of the Court's case law, will be discussed below.⁶⁶

As mentioned above, the Court (together with its Advocate General)⁶⁷ added another factor for assessing whether the breach was "sufficiently serious" – failure by a court of last instance to refer a preliminary question in accordance with Art. 234 EC. This factor is important in connection with the problem of the "disobedient court", mentioned at the beginning of this paper. Furthermore, this is a key element of the System. If a question is resolved by a national court which fails to refer a preliminary question, this provides an individual with means to claim damages and to have its question answered by the Court of Justice, on the "second attempt" as it

⁶² *Anderson D.W.K. Demetriou M. References to the European Court*. London, Sweet & Maxwell, 2002 at p. 143. The authors refer to a case from the UK, *R. v. Commissioners of Customs and Excise, ex parte EMU Tabac* [1995] 3 C.M.L.R. 267 para. 33 where the High Court expressly stated that it did not request a preliminary ruling for the purpose of delaying the procedure. Another case they refer to was *R. v. Manchester Crown Court, ex parte Director of Public Prosecutions* [1993] 1 W.L.R. 693 per Leggatt L.J. 708 E-G, where the prospect of an 18-month delay in a criminal trial was instrumental in persuading the Divisional Court not to make a preliminary reference even though the parties were united in wanting one.

⁶³ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, para. 139.

⁶⁴ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, para. 140.

⁶⁵ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 56.

⁶⁶ See infra section 2.2 at pp. 33-41.

⁶⁷ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, paras. 144-152.

were. For the Court itself, it represents the opportunity to have its say on questions of Community law which would otherwise never be heard and resolved by it.

Art. 234 EC stipulates that a court or tribunal against whose decisions there is no remedy under national law is obliged, when dealing with certain questions of interpretation of Community law, to refer such questions to the Court. The Court widened this obligation to all courts in cases when the validity of a Community act is in question.⁶⁸

In relation to the highest courts, the Court of Justice elaborated upon this obligation in *CILFIT*.⁶⁹ According to the Court, a national judge is not obliged to refer a question of Community law raised in proceedings before him when that question is irrelevant for his decision, or when the Community provision in question has already been interpreted by the Court, or finally when the correct application of Community law is so obvious as to leave no scope for any reasonable doubt.⁷⁰

The last of the conditions, known as *acte claire* stipulates that a national judge has to bear in mind that Community legislation is drafted in several languages, all of which are equally authentic. An interpretation thereof thus involves a comparison of the different language versions. Furthermore, Community law uses terminology which is peculiar to it, and its legal concepts do not necessarily have the same meaning in Community law as in the law of the various Member States. Finally, every provision of Community law must be placed in its context and interpreted in the light of the provisions of Community law as a whole, regard being had to the objectives thereof and to its state of evolution at the date on which the provision in question is to be applied.⁷¹ It is no wonder that some commentators viewed these conditions as being unachievable.⁷² The discussion on unworkable conditions of the *CILFIT* test is submitted later in the paper,⁷³ at this place it should be remarked that in *Köbler* the Court did not make use of the

⁶⁸ Case 314/85 *Foto-Frost v. Hauptzollamt Lübeck-Ost* [1987] ECR 4199.

⁶⁹ Case 283/81 *Srl C.I.L.F.I.T. and Lanificio SpA v. Ministry of Health* [1982] ECR 3430. See further Lenaerts, Arts, Bray 1999 at pp. 45-55 or Schermers, Waelbroeck 2001 at pp. 266-285, Anderson, Demetriou 2002 at pp. 130-186, particularly on *CILFIT* at pp. 173-183.

⁷⁰ *CILFIT*, supra note 69, para. 21.

⁷¹ *Ibid.*, paras. 18-20.

⁷² E.g. *Rasmussen H.* The European Court's Acte Clair Strategy in *C.I.L.F.I.T.* [1984] 9 E.L.Rev. 242.

⁷³ See infra section 3.2 at pp. 50-56.

opportunity to change the test, which is to be regretted from the point of view of the effectiveness of the System.⁷⁴ At the moment the Court does not have a means of filtering the “appeals” (preliminary references on liability actions) and a means of making its case-load more manageable.

1.2.3 (Mis)application of the “sufficiently serious breach” test

The condition of a “sufficiently serious breach” proved to be crucial for the outcome of the Court of Justice’s ruling in *Köbler*. By ruling that the breach did not satisfy this strict test, the Court excluded Austria’s liability and set aside interesting questions regarding e.g. causality of the damage.⁷⁵

However, when adjudicating whether the breach committed by the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof*, the Court disregarded the standard it had set in the judgement, when formulating the conditions of liability on a general level, before applying them to the case of professor Köbler. It merely stated that the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* had infringed Art. 234 EC on the preliminary ruling procedure as interpreted in the *CILFIT*⁷⁶ and the Treaty provisions on the Free Movement of Workers.⁷⁷ When coming to the conclusion that the breach committed was not sufficiently serious, it did not refer to any of the above-mentioned factors. It instead stated that

[i]t was owing to its [the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof*’s] incorrect reading of that judgement that the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* no longer considered it necessary to refer that question of interpretation to the Court.⁷⁸

Under this interpretation, every national court is excused in the case they have “incorrectly read” the judgements of the Court of Justice, and they can always plausibly argue that that is precisely what has occurred. Bearing that in mind, one is justified in asking whether the test of sufficiently

⁷⁴ Such an option was not proposed by AG Léger either. He confirmed the relevance of the *CILFIT* test in para. 146 of his opinion (opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15).

⁷⁵ Cf. *Anagnostaras, G.* The Allocation of Responsibility in State Liability Actions for Breach of Community Law: a Modern Gordian Knot? [2001] 26 E.L.Rev. 139 or *Anagnostaras G.* Not as unproblematic as you might think: the establishment of causation in governmental liability actions. [2002] 27 E.L.Rev. 663.

⁷⁶ See supra pp. 16-17.

⁷⁷ *Köbler* supra note 9, paras. 118, 119.

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*, para. 123, emphases added.

serious breach is of any real consequence for cases of alleged breach of Community law by Member State courts.

We will see that in connection with *Commission v. Italy* that, in creating the System, it was probably the intention of the Court to preserve its cooperative relationship with national courts, by showing its benevolence while at the same defining the principle of liability.⁷⁹

1.3 Kühne & Heitz – does *res judicata* still matter?

The second of the Founding Judgments illustrates well how insignificant may be issues raised by national courts in preliminary ruling procedures. A tariff classification of “chicken legs when pieces of back remain thereon” was to be determined by the Netherlands Administrative Court for Trade and Industry (*College van Beroep voor het bedrijfsleven*). The applicant company, Kühne & Heitz, was in dispute with the competent customs authority since the latter did not classify the goods in question as “chicken legs”. This subsequently has led to Kühne & Heitz’s being liable to reimburse an amount of money received for its exports realized between December 1986 and December 1987. The company appealed this in the *College van Beroep voor het bedrijfsleven*, which nevertheless dismissed the appeal by its judgement from 1991. When ruling in the case, the *College van Beroep* did not refer a preliminary question to the ECJ (nor did the applicant request it do so).

Three years later the Court of Justice in *Voogd Vleesimport en -export*⁸⁰ confirmed Kühne & Heitz’s position had been correct. Following this judgment Kühne & Heitz requested from the customs authority repayment of the refunds which the latter had, in its view, wrongly required it to reimburse.

By an appeal the dispute reached the *College van Beroep* again. That court stated that under Netherlands law, administrative bodies, in principle, always have the power to reopen a final decision. The existence of such a power may, in certain circumstances, imply an obligation to withdraw such a decision. However, the *College van Beroep* considered that judicial decisions given subsequent to a final administrative decision could not, in themselves, affect the finality of

⁷⁹ See infra section 1.4 at pp. 24-29.

⁸⁰ Case C-151/93 *Criminal proceedings against M. Voogd Vleesimport en -export BV* [1994] ECR I-4915.

that decision. In its view this should also apply for ECJ's rulings. The opposite conclusion "would give rise to administrative chaos, seriously impair legal certainty and therefore cannot be accepted".⁸¹ On the other hand the *College van Beroep* mentioned that under Netherlands law subsequent case-law of the European Court of Human Rights may in criminal-law cases have an effect on final decisions if legal remedies have been exhausted.⁸²

In its order of reference to the ECJ the *College van Beroep* made a very extraordinary confession: it stated that when it had ruled on the classification of the chicken legs the first time, it "mistakenly took the view that it was released from [the] obligation [to refer the preliminary question to the ECJ]".⁸³ This may also be one of the reasons it considered the possibility of reopening the administrative decision addressed to the applicant. The *College van Beroep* also pointed to the special position of the applicant, since the latter had exhausted the legal remedies available to it. Furthermore the interpretation of Community law applied by the *College van Beroep* has proved to be contrary to a judgment given subsequently by the ECJ and, finally, the applicant complained to the administrative body immediately after becoming aware of that judgment of the Court.

The *College van Beroep* formulated its preliminary question in the following words:

Under Community law, in particular under the principle of Community solidarity contained in Article 10 EC, and in the circumstances described in the grounds of this decision, is an administrative body required to reopen a decision which has become final in order to ensure the full operation of Community law, as it is to be interpreted in the light of a subsequent preliminary ruling?

All intervening parties⁸⁴ as well as the Commission proposed to answer the question in the negative.⁸⁵ All of them except one⁸⁶ rested their arguments on the principle of legal certainty and *res judicata*. Referring to these principles the Court held that "Community law does not require that administrative bodies be placed under an obligation, in principle, to reopen an administrative

⁸¹ *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 10, para. 15.

⁸² *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 10, para. 16.

⁸³ *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 10, para. 18.

⁸⁴ The Netherlands Government, the French Government and the EFTA Surveillance Authority.

⁸⁵ See Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, paras. 32-35.

⁸⁶ The EFTA Surveillance Authority proposed answering in the negative basing its assertion on the principle of national procedural autonomy. See Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, para. 35.

decision which has become final in that way”.⁸⁷ However, the Court did not exclude such a possibility completely. An administrative authority has an obligation to review a final administrative decision when:

- under national law, it has the power to reopen that decision;
- the administrative decision in question has become final as a result of a judgment of a national court ruling at final instance;
- that judgment is, in the light of a subsequent decision given by the Court, based on a misinterpretation of Community law which was adopted without a question being referred to the Court for a preliminary ruling under Article 234(3) EC; and
- the person concerned complained to the administrative body immediately after becoming aware of that decision of the Court.⁸⁸

The Court therefore seemed to limit to very exceptional situations claims when *res judicata* could be breached. The most important qualification thereto is that a final decision may be reopened only if this is allowed by national law. This echoes one of the fundamental principles of the relationship between Community law and national procedural rules: the principle of national procedural autonomy.⁸⁹ According to this principle,

[i]n the absence of Community rules on this subject, it is for the domestic legal system of each Member State to designate the Courts having jurisdiction and to determine the procedural conditions governing actions at law intended to ensure the protection of the rights which citizens have from the direct effect of Community law.⁹⁰

These domestic rules are only limited by a requirement as to their effectiveness⁹¹ and equality⁹² with rules governing similar actions based on national law. In contrast to its far-reaching rulings

⁸⁷ *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 10, para. 24.

⁸⁸ *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 10, para. 28.

⁸⁹ See e.g. Schermers, Waelbroeck 2001 at pp.199-218 and the literature cited therein.

⁹⁰ Case 33/76 *Rewe-Zentral Finanz eG and Rewe-Zentral AG v. Landwirtschaftskammer für das Saarland* [1976] ECR 1989, para. 5. The principle is in the same words cited by the Court in *Köbler* –see *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 46, with reference to further case-law.

⁹¹ Case 106/77 *Amministrazione delle Finanze dello Stato v. Simmenthal* [1978] ECR 629, paras. 21-23.

e.g. in *Factortame* or *Simmenthal*,⁹³ in the present case the Court was therefore very prudent to allow for limitations which these rules may pose to Community rights claimed by individuals in national courts.

One should not nevertheless be led to the conclusion that such a reopening would occur only in exceptional circumstances. It goes beyond the scope of this paper to make a comparative analysis of national administrative procedures, yet it should be noted that probably every national legal order allows some kind of extraordinary review of administrative decisions as the expression of a general principle of lawful government.⁹⁴ As we see, the power to reopen the decision is not further qualified, thus it could be interpreted very broadly.

Advocate General Léger came to a slightly different solution in his opinion. He started with an analysis of the temporal effects of judgements given in preliminary rulings,⁹⁵ stating that they have, in principle, retroactive effects. They are not constitutive in nature, since they only declare what the correct interpretation of law is. This interpretation must apply from the day of the interpreted act's coming into force, not only from the date of the Court's ruling. Exclusively the Court may limit temporal effect of its rulings and it may only do so in a very exceptional, and at the same time precisely determined situations. Léger pointed out that in *Voogd Vleesimport en – export* the Court did not do so, therefore the application of this judgement is not limited in time.⁹⁶

⁹² Case 88/89 *Roquette Frères SA v. Direction des Services Fiscaux du Pas-de-Calais* [2000] ECR I-10465, para. 29. Interpretation of the principle has been changing in time to a rather narrow application only in cases of straightforward discrimination - Schermers, Waelbroeck 2001 at p. 201.

⁹³ *Simmenthal* supra note 90, Case 213/89 *R. v. Secretary of State for Transport, ex parte Factortame Ltd* [1990] ECR I-2433. Both judgements were cited by AG Léger. He mentioned that in the first of them it was a rule of constitutional nature and in the latter a rule which was well-settled in national law being set aside to allow full effectiveness of Community law - Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, para. 48.

⁹⁴ See *Schönberg S.J. Legal Certainty and Revocation of Administrative decisions: A Comparative Study of English, French and EC Law*. [1999-2000] 19 YB.E.L. 257 for the UK and France. To mention an example of a new Member State, such a possibility exists e.g. in the Czech Rules of Administrative Procedure, Act. No. 71/1967 Col., § 62 (1) b) on the renewal of proceedings, which allows so in case that “[t]he procedure before an administrative body concluded by a decision, which is final and conclusive, shall be renewed on a submission of a party, if the decision depended on an assessment of a preliminary question, which was decided differently by the competent body.” On situation in Austria see infra note 127 and the related text.

⁹⁵ Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, paras. 36-42. See the judgements cited therein.

⁹⁶ Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, para. 43.

Effectiveness of Community law was for Léger the main argument why the *res judicata* principle should not prevent individuals from claiming their Community rights.⁹⁷ He also based his argument on the principle of primacy of Community law and its direct effect. To find a legal basis in the Treaty, he cited Art. 10 EC recalling its application in *Factortame* and *Francovich*.⁹⁸ Referring to *Commisson v. Italy*⁹⁹ he emphasized that Member States had limited their sovereign powers and that no national provisions may be invoked by them to override this limitation.¹⁰⁰

In that line of arguments Léger cited another case in which he had written an opinion at approximately the same time – *Larsy*.¹⁰¹ In this case a Belgian social security authority, *INASTI*,¹⁰² limited Mr. Gervais Larsy's retirement pension since he obtained some pension also in France, where he had also worked and paid social security contributions. Mr. Gervais Larsy brought an action against this decision to a labour tribunal, which nevertheless dismissed it as unfounded without referring a question to the ECJ. Since notice of the judgement was not served, the judgment did not become final. A couple of years later a brother of Mr. Larsy Marius was given the same decision. Hearing the appeal, this time the same court referred a question to the ECJ, which gave an interpretation supporting Marius Larsy's claim in the national court.¹⁰³

Gervais Larsy subsequently requested *INASTI* to reconsider its initial decision. The latter complied with his request; however, since a judgment had been delivered dismissing the action brought against that decision, it asked Mr. Larsy to submit a new application. In the decision thereon *INASTI* limited its retroactive effects, leaving a part of the claimant's benefits non-recovered. It argued that full retroactivity (which would have been allowed if there had been no new application but a complete review of the initial one) was precluded by respective

⁹⁷ Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, paras. 44-45.

⁹⁸ Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, para. 47 - *Factortame* supra note 93, Joined cases C-6/90 and 9/90 *Francovich and Others v. Italy* [1991] ECR I-5357.

⁹⁹ Case 48/71 *Commission of the European Communities v. Italian Republic* [1979] ECR-529.

¹⁰⁰ Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, para. 57. He further referred to case-law of the Court confirming this – see *ibid.* para. 58.

¹⁰¹ Case C-118/00 *Gervais Larsy v. Institut national d'assurances sociales pour travailleurs indépendants (INASTI)* [2001] ECR I-5063.

¹⁰² *Institut national d'assurances sociales pour travailleurs indépendants*.

¹⁰³ In this case it was a brother of the applicant who did not obtain full retirement pension in breach of Community law. In his case the *Tribunal du travail de Tournai* referred a question to the ECJ which gave an interpretation in his favour - Case C-31/92 *Marius Larsy v. Institut National d'Assurances Sociales pour Travailleurs Indépendants* [1993] ECR I-4543.

Community legislation.¹⁰⁴ The claimant thus decided to appeal the judgement of the labour tribunal, which originally dismissed the action against the initial decision of *INASTI* (as we know, it had not become final) and at the same time to claim damages both for non-material and material harm suffered by the second decision of *INASTI* limiting the retroactive effects of the review.

For our purposes the only question that is relevant is whether the judgement dismissing the action against the initial decision of *INASTI* may preclude *INASTI* from full review of its decision. Since such preclusion was based on national rules, the Court has clearly held, in accordance with the principle of primacy of Community law, that it may not. It stated that “to the extent that national procedural rules precluded effective protection of Mr Larsy's rights derived under the direct effect of Community law, [*INASTI*] should have disapplied those provisions”.¹⁰⁵

Léger in *Kühne & Heitz* was aware that *Larsy* and the case before him were distinguishable on the facts, namely that in *Larsy* the judgement of the labour tribunal which precluded *INASTI* from complete review of its initial decision was not in fact *res judicata*. However he did not consider these differences substantial and applied *Larsy* to *Kühne & Heitz*, stating that

[The] principle of primacy precludes national administration to refuse to comply with a request of an individual based on Community law on grounds that this request tends to undermine a previous administrative decision which was not changed by a judicial decision and which therefore become *res judicata*.¹⁰⁶

In contrast to the Court, the Advocate General was not so tied to the principle of national procedural autonomy. He deduced that, as this principle had been interpreted by the Court, it concerned only the procedural exercise of a Community right, not the very existence thereof.¹⁰⁷

¹⁰⁴ Article 95a(5) of Regulation (EEC) No 1408/71 of the Council of 14 June 1971 on the application of social security schemes to employed persons and their families moving within the Community OJ 1971 L 149/2. This was also based on incorrect interpretation thereof – see *Larsy*, supra note 101, paras. 46-49.

¹⁰⁵ *Larsy*, supra note 101, para. 53.

¹⁰⁶ Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, para. 66: “[Le] principe de primauté s'oppose à ce qu'une administration nationale refuse de faire droit à une demande d'un particulier fondée sur le droit communautaire au motif que cette demande tendrait à remettre en cause une décision administrative antérieure qui n'aurait pas été censurée par une décision juridictionnelle, que celle-ci soit revêtue de l'autorité de la chose jugée ou de l'autorité de la chose définitivement jugée.” Translation from French by the author.

¹⁰⁷ Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, para. 70.

In his view, it is in line with this principle to limit the exercise of this right in time for the sake of legal certainty. Léger states that Community law does not require national administrative authorities to reopen their final decisions. However, in order to ensure the effective protection of individuals' Community rights, national authorities must find appropriate ways of protecting individuals' Community rights breached by those decisions.¹⁰⁸ Léger did not give any guidance as to how to determine these ways.

In conclusion, we will see further in this paper how this judgement may operate in conjunction with *Köbler*. However, even in isolation we see that the Court laid another brick of the System: if a national court hearing an appeal against a decision of an administrative authority improperly fails to refer a preliminary question, an individual may not be imprisoned in his national judicial system – he has an opportunity to contest this decision for the second time, if the conditions defined in *Kühne & Heitz* are fulfilled.

1.4 *Commission v. Italy* – the Guardian of the Treaty v. the Courts' interlocutors

In this case the Commission instituted an action against Italy because the latter maintained in force Art. 29(2) of the law implementing obligations resulting from Italy's membership in the EU (hereinafter "Community Law 1990").¹⁰⁹ This law, as construed and applied by the administrative authorities and the courts, governed rules of evidence in relation to the passing on to third parties of the amount of charges levied in breach of Community rules. Such rules of evidence had been previously held by the Court to be in breach of Community law.¹¹⁰ Although the original law, which gave rise to these findings, had been amended in 1990, further references from Italian courts followed.¹¹¹ They showed that the law was still applied by the Italian courts to the effect that, in order to resist the repayment of customs duties or taxes paid in breach of Community law, the administration might rely on the presumption that such duties and taxes

¹⁰⁸ Opinion of AG Léger in *Kühne & Heitz NV*, supra note 15, para. 74.

¹⁰⁹ Law No 428 of 29 December 1990 entitled Disposizioni per l'adempimento di obblighi derivanti dall'appartenenza dell'Italia alle Comunità europee (legge comunitaria per il 1990) (Provisions for the fulfilment of obligations deriving from Italy's membership of the European Communities (Community law for 1990), (GURI No 10 of 12 January 1991, Ordinary Supplement, p. 5 - see *Commission v. Italy*, supra note 11, para. 1.

¹¹⁰ Case 199/82 *Amministrazione delle Finanze dello Stato v. SpA San Giorgio* [1983] ECR 3595 and Case 104/86 *Commission of the European Communities v. Italian Republic* [1988] ECR 1799. In these cases the law which preceded the Law from 1990 was examined by the Court

¹¹¹ Case C-343/96 *Dilexport Srl v. Amministrazione delle Finanze dello Stato* [1999] ECR I-579.

were normally passed on to third parties. This presumption had to be rebutted by a taxpayer seeking repayment.

In its application, the Commission particularly pointed out the practice of the Supreme Court of Appeal (*Corte suprema di cassazione*) which was followed by many other trial courts in Italy.¹¹² This was a surprising allegation, since it was the first time the Commission addressed so openly that an alleged infringement consisted in a national judiciary's misapplication of Community law. The view taken insofar had been to overlook such misapplication, not that much because of it being tolerable, but rather because of the sensitivity involved in "condemning" a national judiciary.¹¹³ Such a position was explicitly confirmed by the Commission itself.¹¹⁴

The Court of Justice itself, at the beginning of its reasoning in the analysed case, referred to its settled case-law, which confirmed that

[a] Member State's failure to fulfil obligations may, in principle, be established under Article 226 EC whatever the agency of that State whose action or inaction is the cause of the failure to fulfil its obligations, even in the case of a constitutionally independent institution.¹¹⁵

This, together with another ruling cited by the Court, which states that "[t]he scope of national laws, regulations or administrative provisions must be assessed in the light of the interpretation

¹¹² *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 11, paras. 11-16. However, the Commission also mentioned the practice of Italian administrative authorities leading to the infringement – *ibid.*, para. 17. See also opinion of AG Geelhoed in *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 15, para. 24 and in particular para. 27.

¹¹³ See e.g. Schermers, Waelbroeck 2001 at pp. 630-631 or in context of a breach of the obligation to refer a preliminary question according to Art. 234 EC see Lenaerts, Arts, Bray 1999 at p. 52. The latter nevertheless generally confirms such a possibility in case of deliberately ignoring or disregarding of Community law by a national court – *ibid.*, at p. 98. AG Geelhoed referred to academic literature confirming such a possibility in note 22 of his opinion (opinion of AG Geelhoed in *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 15).

¹¹⁴ See e.g. Seventh Annual Report to the European Parliament on Monitoring the Application of Community Law for 1989, COM (90) 288 final, also published in [1990] O.J. C 232/1, at p. 232/54, para. 5, mentioning a situation when the Commission had firstly noticed that it would bring an action against France and subsequently disclaimed such an action saying that the proceedings is on a way of its resolution in cooperation between French authorities and the Commission's services. In its written reply to the question of Member of the European Parliament Tyrell the Commission recalled the cooperative relationship between the ECJ and national courts when asserting that an infringement procedure could disrupt it. See Written question No. 526/83 of 9 June 1983, OJ 1983 C 268/25.

¹¹⁵ *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 11, para. 29 referring to Case 77/69 *Commission of the European Communities v. Kingdom of Belgium* [1970] ECR 237, para. 15.

given to them by national courts”,¹¹⁶ could leave the impression that the Court was trying to justify a ruling finding an infringement based on the actions of the judiciary.

The Court even stated that Art. 29(2) of the Community Law 1990 was in itself neutral in respect of Community law and that it, therefore, must be examined in light of the interpretation given to it by Italian courts. The Court was stressing that

[i]n that regard, isolated or numerically insignificant judicial decisions in the context of case-law taking a different direction, or still more a construction disowned by the national supreme court, cannot be taken into account. That is not true of a widely-held judicial construction which has not been disowned by the supreme court, but rather confirmed by it.¹¹⁷

However, the Court did not go so far, and it shifted its argumentation in the very next paragraph. The Court stated there that Italian legislation was insufficiently clear, since it had been subject to different judicial interpretations, some of them leading to infringements of Community law.¹¹⁸ After examining the jurisprudence of the *Corte suprema di cassazione* and the practice of administrative authorities, approved by that court, the Court of Justice came to the conclusion that the infringement occurred not as a result of the action of the judiciary, but as a consequence of Italy’s

[f]ailing to amend Article 29(2) of [Community Law 1990], which is construed and applied by the administrative authorities and a substantial proportion of the courts, including the *Corte suprema di cassazione*, in such a way that the exercise of the right to repayment of charges levied in breach of Community rules is made excessively difficult for the taxpayer [...].¹¹⁹

It was a very diplomatic solution of the Court’s dilemma, balancing between, on the one hand, the effectiveness of Community law, which would have been enhanced by an express

¹¹⁶ *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 11, para. 30 referring to Case C-382/92 *Commission of the European Communities v. United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland* [1994] ECR I-2435, para. 36.

¹¹⁷ *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 11, para. 32. This statement of the Court echoed the opinion of Advocate General Warner in Case 30/77 *Régina v. Pierre Bouchereau* [1977] ECR 1999 at p. 2020, who then submitted that “[a] Member State cannot be held to have failed to fulfil an obligation under the Treaty simply because one of its courts has reached a wrong decision. [...] Judicial error is not a breach of the Treaty. [...] Art. 169 [now Art. 226] could only come into play in the event of a court of a Member State deliberately ignoring or disregarding Community law” (cited in Schermers, Waëlbroeck 2001 at p. 630).

¹¹⁸ *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 11, para. 33.

¹¹⁹ *Commission v. Italy*, *supra* note 11, para. 41.

condemnation of a Member State for breaches committed by its judiciary, and, on the other hand, the preservation of the cooperative relationship with national courts. The latter would be in danger had the Court acted too harshly against its national interlocutors. Contrary to *Köbler*, the Court in this case was not forced to find an infringement solely on a basis of a judicial act, and it availed itself of the possibility to circumvent this.

As the nature of an advocate general opinion allows for it, Advocate General Geelhoed dealt with the question of judicial infringements in more detail.¹²⁰ We will see that his detailed examination of the issues raised by the case prepared the ground for the above-described diplomatic solution adopted by the Court.

Like Advocate General Léger in *Köbler*, Geelhoed referred to the Court's established practice of viewing a State as a single entity, and a distinction may not be made between constitutional authorities in reference to the national rules governing the division of powers within the State.¹²¹

The difference from *Köbler* lay in the fact that *Commission v. Italy* dealt with decisions of not only a supreme court of a Member State, but also of its inferior courts. Although emphasising the key role which national supreme courts play in the system of Community judiciary (Geelhoed mentioned the preliminary ruling procedure, in which these courts may be the last chance to achieve a correct interpretation and application of Community law by sending a reference to the ECJ), he also said that "inferior national judges do not remain less responsible" even though "their decisions are susceptible of being corrected within the national legal order".¹²² According to Geelhoed, the difference between supreme courts and inferior courts lies in the fact that single (isolated) decisions of the latter alone cannot give rise to State responsibility. On the contrary, this may be the case of a decision of a supreme court, which is considered authoritative by inferior judges. The further distinguishing factor is that decisions of supreme courts cannot be corrected within the national legal order.

¹²⁰ AG Geelhoed is analysing the mere possibility of holding a Member State responsible for the functioning of its judiciary in paras. 48-61 of his opinion (opinion of AG Geelhoed in *Commission v. Italy*, supra note 15).

¹²¹ Opinion of AG Geelhoed in *Commission v. Italy*, supra note 15, paras. 50-53.

¹²² Opinion of AG Geelhoed in *Commission v. Italy*, supra note 15, para. 59, translation from French by the author.

Nonetheless Geelhoed does not exclude that individuals would be discouraged from making appeals against decisions of inferior courts should these courts in a systematic fashion interpret and apply Community law in an erroneous manner. These decisions would not therefore be corrected by supreme courts. Accordingly, regardless of the status of inferior court decisions in the national legal order, it is still possible to find that an infringement results therefrom.¹²³

When concluding that a national judiciary may also invoke an infringement of Community law, Geelhoed had in mind the difficulties the State in question may meet when trying to remedy the infringement. The independence of the judiciary does not allow direct intervention into its decision-making. On the face of this Member States seem to not have means to avoid a subsequent procedure under Art. 228 EC for failure to comply with the judgment of the ECJ establishing such infringement.

Arguments presented by the Advocate General in reply to this prepared the way for the Court to avoid making an express finding that the Italian courts are responsible for the infringement. He stated that in such a situation a national legislator must take corrective action so as not to allow courts practice which infringes Treaty obligations.¹²⁴ Similarly to the Court's judgement, he then concluded that the infringement was not caused by the case-law of the Italian courts itself, but by omission of Italian legislator to amend Art. 29(2) of the Community Law 1990.¹²⁵

2 READING THE FOUNDING JUDGEMENTS IN CONTEXT – THE SYSTEM CREATED

2.1 *Köbler* and *Kühne & Heitz*: appellate procedure through the backdoors

The judgement of the Court in *Köbler* does not necessarily represent the end of the story. Let us put *Köbler* in the context of *Kühne & Heitz*.

In *Köbler* the Court clearly held that the decision of the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* was based on an incorrect interpretation of Community law. Even though the decision of that court did not breach Community law in a “sufficiently serious manner”, that does not mean that Mr. Köbler will not be able to claim the contested increments.

¹²³ Opinion of AG Geelhoed in *Commission v. Italy*, supra note 15, para. 63.

¹²⁴ Opinion of AG Geelhoed in *Commission v. Italy*, supra note 15, para. 66.

¹²⁵ Opinion of AG Geelhoed in *Commission v. Italy*, supra note 15, para. 117.

Kühne & Heitz states that an administrative body is under an obligation to re-open its final decision when four conditions are met.¹²⁶ It is submitted that Mr. Köbler could have satisfied all of them. The relevant provision of the Austrian Rules of Administrative Procedure allows him to ask the administrative body which in the very beginning decided not to grant him the contested increments to re-open that decision (the first condition).¹²⁷ The negative administrative decision was upheld by the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof*, which decided in the last instance without asking for a preliminary ruling properly. Mr. Köbler has the Court's of Justice judgement given in *Köbler* showing that the decision of the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* was based on a misinterpretation of Community law (the second and the third condition). If he were to come to the administrative authority immediately (the fourth condition), there is nothing to prevent him from getting the increment – according to *Kühne & Heitz* at least.

It would give rise to a very fantastic scenario were the administrative authority to refuse once again to grant him the increment. Mr. Köbler may go to a court to claim damages again, this time for the breach committed by this second denial of the administrative authority to give him his Community right. In line with *Larsy*,¹²⁸ there is a great probability that this time Mr. Köbler would be successful. As we remember, in this case Mr. Larsy also claimed damages since when *INASTI* was reconsidering its original decision it limited retroactive effects of the new one. At the time of this reconsideration, there was a clear interpretation given by the Court of Justice in case of Mr. Larsy's brother. Accessing the questions referred by the Labour Tribunal hearing the damages action of Mr. Larsy, the Court of Justice recalled that:

[a] breach of Community law will be sufficiently serious if it has persisted despite a preliminary ruling from the Court from which it is clear that the conduct in question constituted an infringement.¹²⁹

The same should apply if the administrative authority in Austria were to fail to “draw all the consequences from [the] judgment[s] of the Court”¹³⁰ in *Köbler* and *Kühne & Heitz*. In such a case there would be a “sufficiently serious breach” and Mr. Köbler would be entitled to

¹²⁶ See supra pp. 23-24.

¹²⁷ Allgemeines Verwaltungsverfahren-Gesetz 1991 (AVG) BGBl. 51/1991, § 69 (1) 3. This provision is essentially the same as the relevant provision of the Czech Rules of Administrative Procedure cited in supra note 94.

¹²⁸ *Larsy*, supra note 101. For the facts of the case see pp. 22-23.

¹²⁹ *Ibid.*, para. 44.

¹³⁰ Cf. the wording of the judgement in *Larsy*, *ibid.*, para. 45.

reparation. Be that as it may, Mr. Köbler would probably eventually obtain what he had been seeking for several years.

Our point here is that this possibility opens a way for all individuals whose Community right was violated by a national court which failed to refer a question to the Court of Justice and upheld an unlawful administrative decision. Now, if a national court commits such an infringement, an individual may claim damages, as *Köbler* states. Moreover, one should not be deterred by the restrictive conditions of the “sufficiently serious breach test” (or their actual mis/application by the Court in *Köbler*). At this stage the principal thing is to obtain an interpretation of Community law given by the Court of Justice. Even though the failure to refer would not be considered to be a “sufficiently serious breach” and there would not be any reparation, the Court will give its interpretation on the right allegedly breached. With this in hands the individual may turn back to an administrative authority giving the initial decision and ask for it to be re-opened. The first condition of the test, the permissibility under national law of re-opening administrative decisions, should not be such a hurdle since, as the expression of a general principle of lawful government, it probably exists in most national administrative laws, as an example of Austria, England, France or the Czech Republic (as a representative of the new Member States) shows.¹³¹

One may say that it still depends whether a national court hearing the liability claim would ever refer a question thereon. It is submitted that such court will refer with a great probability.

We saw that in *Köbler* the *Landesgericht für Zivilrechtssachen* was asking the Court to rule on the question whether *all* the conditions of liability are fulfilled. It was rather extraordinary for a national court to ask the Court of Justice to do something like this. The general trend in liability cases has been to leave national courts to decide as much as they could, since they were best situated to apply the criteria of liability to the facts of the case before them.¹³² However, in *Köbler* another consideration prevailed over this one: it is difficult for a national court to decide on a breach of law allegedly committed by another court.¹³³ It is submitted that a national court in

¹³¹ See supra note 94.

¹³² See Tridimas 2001 at pp. 316 and 332.

¹³³ In *Köbler*, the court having allegedly committed the breach (*Verwaltungsgerichtshof*) was an administrative court and the court hearing the liability action (*Landesgericht*) was a court pertaining to another (civil) jurisdiction. *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* was therefore not a superior court to *Landesgericht*. Nevertheless this could easily happen, if

such delicate situation will probably rather refer the case than decide it itself. It is indeed something proposed by Advocate General Léger in *Köbler* when discussing doubts on national courts' impartiality when they "judge other judges". He states:

Indeed in order to dispel any reasonable doubt as to its impartiality, the national court might choose to refer a question for a preliminary ruling and thus entrust to the Court the responsibility of examining whether the supreme court concerned has in fact acted in breach of Community law and, if so, to what extent. Recourse to such a procedure would offer a dual advantage since it would make it possible both to dispel any reasonable doubt as to the impartiality of the national court and to give guidance to that court in this delicate exercise by avoiding the risk of error in the appraisal of an alleged error.¹³⁴

Although Léger compares the Court of Justice to the European Court of Human rights as an independent international court capable of hearing *individual* complaints, according to him "it would be excessive to infer that such a situation would lead to the establishment of a final remedy that is to make the Court a final court of appeal".¹³⁵ However, he is not very persuasive in his rhetoric, to the effect that the preliminary ruling procedure is not "anything other than the expression of a mechanism of judicial cooperation founded on the logic of dialogue and mutual trust between courts"¹³⁶. Formally, it is exclusively for a national court to decide whether or not it refers an issue to the Court; however, *in fact*, the national court will probably do so in order to avoid judging another court and submit this court's judgement to the Court's of Justice scrutiny. This court is further forced to submit the preliminary reference to the Court of Justice by *Commission v. Italy*. If it would be "widely-held judicial construction"¹³⁷ of national courts to deny possibility of judicial breaches of Community law, a possible Commission's action pursuant to Art. 226 may serve as a deterrent factor against this. Therefore we may speak *cum grano salis* about an appellate procedure rather than the judicial cooperation.

However, the argument here is that it is not only individuals who benefit from this situation. For the Court it means that individuals may serve as vehicles bringing to the courtrooms in

the court committing the breach was a civil court. Then the incentive to "let Luxembourg decide" would even greater.

¹³⁴ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, para. 111.

¹³⁵ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, para. 112.

¹³⁶ *Ibid.*

¹³⁷ See supra note 117.

Luxembourg questions of Community law, otherwise not referred by “disobedient” national courts. This is important for the Court, since it “shall ensure that in the interpretation and application of [the EC] Treaty the law is observed.”¹³⁸ The Court understands this obligation as ensuring *uniform* interpretation and application of Community law in all Member States, which is reflected as early as in 1974 in *Rheinmühlen*, in connection to preliminary ruling procedure:

[A]rticle 177 [now Article 234 EC] is essential for the preservation of the Community character of the law established by the Treaty and has the object of ensuring that *in all circumstances this law is the same in all states of the Community*.¹³⁹

The Court explains the reason why uniformity is so important in the following words:

Any weakening, even if only potential, of the uniform application and interpretation of Community law throughout the Union would be liable to give rise to distortions of competition and discrimination between economic operators, thus jeopardising equality of opportunity as between those operators and consequently the proper functioning of the internal market.¹⁴⁰

Indeed, it must cause the Court frustration to observe national courts deciding questions of Community law themselves without allowing the Court to give its own interpretation thereon. Allowing individuals to sue the Member States, whose courts are trying to circumvent the Court, thus gives the Court an opportunity to have a say in the dispute as well as the possibility to achieve the desired unity of the Community legal order.

2.2 ‘The Authority of Judgements of the European Court of Justice’ revisited

In 1984 A.G. Toth published his study on binding force and legal effects of the Court’s case-law.¹⁴¹ We will take it as a background for our discussion, since it is one of the most detailed

¹³⁸ Art. 220 EC.

¹³⁹ Case 166/73 *Rheinmühlen-Düsseldorf v. Einfuhr- und Vorratsstelle für Getreide und Futtermittel* [1974] ECR 33, para. 2, emphasis added.

¹⁴⁰ *Report of the Court of Justice on certain aspects of the application of the Treaty on European Union*, Luxembourg, May 1995, http://europa.eu.int/en/agenda/igc-home/eu-doc/justice/cj_rep.html (24.6.2004), point 11.

¹⁴¹ *Toth A.G. The Authority of Judgements of the European Court of Justice: Binding Force and Legal Effects*. [1984] 4 YB. E.L. 1.

studies on the Court's precedents published in English so far. We will also discuss opinions of other authors who dealt with this topic.¹⁴²

Toth distinguished between binding force and legal effects of a judgement of the Court. While the former "simply means that the judgement has the force of law: all those to whom it applies are under a legal obligation to comply with it. It implies a command that the judgement 'must be obeyed' or 'carried into effect'",¹⁴³ legal effects of a judgement refer to a situation when the latter "produces legal effects upon persons to whom they are not addressed and upon whom they are consequently not legally binding".¹⁴⁴ He found that judgements of the Court certainly have legal effects beyond the scope of the case, however that "[n]either the European Court, nor the national courts, or third parties, are legally obliged to follow the Court's judgements in subsequent cases."¹⁴⁵

According to Toth, we must further distinguish degrees of binding force in the Court's case-law. If a national court is bound to follow the case-law, but is allowed to deviate if there are good reasons to do so, the case-law only has persuasive authority. In the other hand, if the case-law is to be followed in every case, however good the reasons for not doing so may be, it is of binding authority.¹⁴⁶ It will be argued in this section that the case-law of the Court is of binding, and not merely persuasive, authority, which follows from a line of case-law beginning with *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III*.

¹⁴² *Barceló J.J.* Precedent in European Community Law. In: *MacCormick N., Summers R.S. (eds.) Interpreting Precedents. A Comparative Study.* Dartmouth, Ashgate, 1997, 407-436, *Bebr G.* Preliminary Rulings of the Court of Justice: Their Authority and Temporal Effect. [1981] 18 C.M.L.Rev. 475, *Koopmans T.* *Stare decisis* in European Law. In: O'Keeffe D., Schermers H.G. *Essays in European Law and Integration*, Deventer, Kluwer, 1982, 11-27.

¹⁴³ Toth 1984 at p. 5.

¹⁴⁴ *Ibid.* at p. 44.

¹⁴⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁴⁶ *Ibid.* at p. 20. The same distinction is made by Koopmans, who refers to the same treatise on English precedents as Toth. Koopmans 1982 at 20. On the other hand, Bebr considers preliminary rulings on validity to have binding force and interpretative rulings as well in case of courts of final instance, which according to him follows from *Da Costa*. (Joined cases 28 to 30/62 *Da Costa en Schaake NV, Jacob Meijer NV, Hoechst-Holland NV v. Netherlands Inland Revenue Administration* [1963] ECR 31 – English special edition). Bebr 1981 at p. 483. Bengoetxea makes a similar distinction using different terminology – should-sources (persuasive authority) and ought-sources (binding authority) – Bengoetxea J. *The Legal Reasoning of the European Court of Justice*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1993 at p. 69.

We will not make distinction between different kinds of judgments the Court may give within its jurisdiction.¹⁴⁷ Because of the argument we use, there is no need to make it. Therefore we will not consider distinctions between Court's ruling in action for annulment nor between interpretative preliminary rulings and preliminary rulings on validity.¹⁴⁸

What F. Jacobs commented as regards preliminary ruling is rather the desirable state of things than the uncontested truth:

[R]ulings given by the ECJ are applied not only by the court which made a reference, but also by all courts in the EU before which the same question arises. That of course is the rationale of the system, which is to enable the law to be applied uniformly throughout the Union.¹⁴⁹

Drawing a parallel from the English doctrine of precedent, Toth is opposed to recognising the binding force of the Court's case-law. Basing himself on a treatise on precedent in English law,¹⁵⁰ he identifies seven key conditions for the application of the doctrine in Community law.¹⁵¹

They are firstly whether Community law is based on case-law as English law; he concludes that it is not, it "came into existence, so to speak 'by one stroke', at a precise moment in time, on the entry into force of the prospective Treaties".¹⁵² This will hardly be ever changed. However, one may ask whether it is really so essential for the case-law to be binding to be established in the case-law-originated legal system. It is submitted, that it is not. Koopmans introduces a similar precondition, i.e. whether the legal system is based mainly on unwritten rules. One may say that the Treaties *are* written rules, however if we examine them closely, we must come to the conclusion together with Koopmans, that "the main rules for judicial activities are unwritten: the treaties are practically silent on the relationship between Community law and national legislators, and criteria for assessing the legality of Community decisions are expressed in a way which [...]"

¹⁴⁷ See Arts. 220-245 EC.

¹⁴⁸ Which become important after the Court's ruling in Case 66/80 *SpA International Chemical Corporation v Amministrazione delle finanze dello Stato* [1981] ECR 1191. See e.g. Bebr 1981.

¹⁴⁹ *Jacobs F.G.* Judicial Dialogue and Cross-Fertilization of Legal Systems: The European Court of Justice. [2003] 38 *Tex. Int'l L.J.* 547.

¹⁵⁰ Cross R. *Precedent in English Law*. 3rd Ed. Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1977.

¹⁵¹ Toth 1984 at pp. 26-27. Interesting to note is that although T. Koopmans founds himself on the same treatise, he sets different (and only three) conditions: 1. the main rules of the system are unwritten, 2. courts have unifying role in a legal system characterized by centrifugal forces, 3. the system necessitates resorting to principles; he concludes that all the three are fulfilled in case of the Community legal order. Koopmans 1982 at pp. 14-17.

¹⁵² Toth 1984 at p. 27.

leaves much room ...”.¹⁵³ D. Keeling equally asserts that “the authors of the Treaty manifestly intended the Court of Justice to perform an active law-making function. No-one would pretend that provisions such as Articles [28-30] contain anything remotely approaching a complete code of rules governing trade in goods between Member States”.¹⁵⁴ Therefore to say that Community law emerged ‘by one stroke’ seems to be a great exaggeration at least. To the contrary, Community law has been emerging gradually and the Court of Justice has played a principal role in this process.

The second condition proposed by Toth would be whether the rules of precedent may develop as a result of the practice of courts. He negates this, arguing that “it is beyond the power of the Court and the scope of its judgements to determine effects of its judgements upon subsequent cases [...], this could only be done by the Treaties”.¹⁵⁵ According to Toth, the Court is not doing so either by a long and continuous practice, whereby it would follow its case-law and require national courts to do the same. He argues that when citing a previous judgement, the rule of law applied in the later case is not derived from the former, but from another source. The Court only “applies an abstract ruling to identical legal situations, in the absence of new legal factors or arguments.” This abstract ruling is however based on another source of law, not a previous judgement of the Court. The previous judgement is not a source of validity of the latter.¹⁵⁶

It is also contestable. Although rhetorically basing its rulings on the text of the Treaty or the principles derived therefrom, the border-line between mere interpreting and law-making may be very vague. One of the examples may be the principle of Member States liability, according to the Court “*inherent* in the system of the Treaty”,¹⁵⁷ yet in the view of one commentator “[going] well beyond the terms of the relevant treaties and legislation”.¹⁵⁸

¹⁵³ Koopmans 1982 at p. 15.

¹⁵⁴ *Keeling D.T.* In Praise of Judicial Activism. But What Does It Mean? And Has the Court of Justice ever Practised It? In: Gialdino C.(ed.), *Scritti in onore di Giuseppe Federico Mancini, Vol. II Diritto Dell’Unione Europea*, Milan, Dott. A. Giuffrè Editore, 1998, 505-536 at pp. 511-512.

¹⁵⁵ *Ibid.* at p. 29.

¹⁵⁶ *Ibid.* at p. 31.

¹⁵⁷ *Francovich*, supra note 98, para. 35, emphasis added.

¹⁵⁸ *Pfander J.E.* Member State Liability and Constitutional Challenge in the United States and Europe. [2003] 51 *Am.J.Comp.L.* 237 at p. 248. For examples of ‘legislative judgements’ of the Court see e.g. *Dowrick F.E.* A Model of the European Communities’ Legal System. [1983] 3 *YB.E.L.* 169 in note 127.

Existence of a hierarchy of the Community courts is the third Toth's condition. The Court denied any hierarchy amongst the Community judiciary as early as in 1960 in *Humblet*.¹⁵⁹ We will see below that the Court is trying to sustain this view even when creating the System we are describing here.¹⁶⁰ It will nevertheless be shown, that a hierarchy is not an essential prerequisite for the Court's case-law to have binding authority.

Fourthly, overruling; Toth wrote his article before *HAG II*¹⁶¹ and *Keck*,¹⁶² of express overruling known until today, thus although he did not acknowledge this element, it is clearly present now.

Fifthly, whether one may distinguish between *ratio decidendi* and *obiter dictum*. "Such a distinction is an essential foundation of the doctrine since the only part of a judicial decision which is legally binding is its *ratio decidendi*".¹⁶³ Toth finds that it is hard to identify the ratio in the Court's judgements and moreover, that the Court does not attach great importance to the distinction, since it is "capable of developing major principles and even legally binding rules from *obiter dicta*".¹⁶⁴ This is true and it represents a problem when discussing the binding authority of the Court's judgements. It goes against legal certainty when it is not sure what is really binding in the judgement. Still, a judgement may have a binding authority (or the latter may be claimed) without this distinction. To formulate a comprehensive normative theory of precedents, how they operate in Community law goes beyond the scope of this paper. However, it would be more than desirable to do so.

Sixthly, whether distinguishing is a part of the Court's reasoning. Although distinguishing is bound with possibility to find *ratio decidendi* and *obiter dictum* of a judgment, which is still hard in judgments of the Court of Justice, examples when the Court thoroughly examines its previous decisions and finds ways how to apply them in different circumstances may be found. Take e.g.

¹⁵⁹ Case 6/60 *Jean-E. Humblet v. Belgian State* [1960] ECR 559 at p. 572. See Toth 1984 at pp. 33-36.

¹⁶⁰ See infra section 2.3 at pp. 38-42.

¹⁶¹ Case C-10/89 *SA CNL-SUCAL NV v. HAG GF AG* [1990] ECR I-3711.

¹⁶² Joined Cases C-267/91 and C-268/91 *Criminal proceedings against Bernard Keck and Daniel Mithouard* [1993] ECR I-6097. See, however, note 160 infra.

¹⁶³ Toth 1984 at p. 36.

¹⁶⁴ *Ibid.* at p. 41.

Überseering,¹⁶⁵ which dealt with free movement of companies. In a previous case, *Daily Mail*, the Court held that

[u]nder those circumstances, Articles 52 and 58 of the Treaty [now 43 and 48] cannot be interpreted as conferring on companies incorporated under the law of a Member State a right to transfer their central management and control and their central administration to another Member State while retaining their status as companies incorporated under the legislation of the first Member State.¹⁶⁶

Überseering concerned the law applicable to recognition of companies incorporated in another state (the Netherlands), particularly when the receiving state's company law (Germany) was based on the real-seat theory, which attaches the legal existence of the company to the place where the main centre of administration is to be found. Intervening states whose laws were based on this theory tried to find support in *Daily Mail*.¹⁶⁷ The Court however rejected their arguments stating that

[i]t must be stressed that, unlike *Daily Mail and General Trust*, which concerned relations between a company and the Member State under whose laws it had been incorporated in a situation where the company wished to transfer its actual centre of administration to another Member State whilst retaining its legal personality in the State of incorporation, the present case concerns the recognition by one Member State of a company incorporated under the law of another Member State, such a company being denied all legal capacity in the host Member State where it takes the view that the company has moved its actual centre of administration to its territory, irrespective of whether in that regard the company actually intended to transfer its seat.¹⁶⁸

Thus the Court distinguished *Daily Mail* on the base of its facts, as a Common Law court would do in case when it would intend to not follow precedent.¹⁶⁹

¹⁶⁵ Case C-208/00 *Überseering BV v Nordic Construction Company Baumanagement GmbH (NCC)* [2002] ECR I-9919.

¹⁶⁶ Case 81/87 *The Queen v H. M. Treasury and Commissioners of Inland Revenue, ex parte Daily Mail and General Trust plc.* [1988] ECR 5483, para. 24.

¹⁶⁷ Germany, Spain, Italy – See *Überseering*, op. cit. supra 165, paras. 29-32.

¹⁶⁸ *Überseering*, op. cit. supra 165, para. 62.

¹⁶⁹ See also Case C-308/93 *Bestuur van de Sociale Verzekeringsbank v. J.M. Cabanis-Issarte* [1996] ECR I-2097, para. 34, where the Court after a thorough analysis of its previous case-law limited its application to specified factual situation. The Court also restricted temporal effect of the judgement – see paras. 46-48. It is disputable whether it was distinguishing or overruling.

Lastly, the kind of relationship between judicial decision and legislation. Contrary to English law, no legislation may abrogate the effects of the Court's decisions. Toth claims that "because of the finality of the Court's decisions and because of the inability of Community legislation to amend their effects, the only way in which unsatisfactory or obsolete decision could be 'overruled' or 'reversed' would be by Treaty amendment – a procedure of extreme complexity which in practice can only be resorted to in truly exceptional situations".¹⁷⁰ We have seen however, that the Court may overrule its previous decisions and that reversing of the judgements of the Court is not so extraordinary for the Member States.¹⁷¹

Toth himself points out that the difficulties which surround the topic of the binding force of the Court's case-law, arise from

[t]he tendency to attempt the problem by a more or less mechanical application of terms and concepts (or, if one prefers, rules and principles) of national law. This is, of course, to ignore the fact that the Community law, as a 'new legal order' of a *sui generis* type with a Court of Justice exercising a unique jurisdiction, requires *sui generis* solutions which are specifically adapted to its own particular requirements.¹⁷²

It seems that when applying the English doctrine of precedent to Community courts, he made the same mistake. Principles of the English doctrine of precedents are simply not transferable to Community law. This nevertheless does not exclude the binding authority of the Court's case-law, as well as it does not exclude the existence of a doctrine of precedent in Community law.

Moreover, the development of Community law has shown that some of his preposition has changed in time. The preposition that for an obligation of national courts to follow case-law of the Court to exist "it is necessary that there be a relationship of hierarchical subordination between the national courts and the European Court"¹⁷³ may be false.

¹⁷⁰ Toth 1984 at p. 43.

¹⁷¹ It happened by the Protocols amended to the Treaties at the Maastricht IGC in 1992 – e.g. Protocol (No 2) concerning Article 119 of the Treaty establishing the European Community, the so-called "Barber Protocol" giving an interpretation to the judgement in Case C-262/88 *Douglas Harvey Barber v. Guardian Royal Exchange Assurance Group* 1990] ECR I-1889. For further examples of the "political overruling" see Dehousse R. *The European Court of Justice. The Politics of Judicial Integration*. London, MacMillan Press, 1998 at pp. 162-172.

¹⁷² Toth 1984 at p. 4.

¹⁷³ *Ibid.* at p. 33.

The Court may bind national courts without establishing a hierarchy *stricto sensu*. It has in fact done so by attaching a sanction of a liability in case of not following its previous case-law. It was seen as early as in *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III*:

On any view, a breach of Community law will clearly be sufficiently serious if it has persisted despite a judgement finding the infringement in question to be established, or a preliminary ruling or settled case-law of the Court on the matter from which it is clear that the conduct in question constituted an infringement.¹⁷⁴

In *Köbler* the Court was briefer when only stating that:

In any event, an infringement of Community law will be sufficiently serious where the decision [of a national court] concerned was made in manifest breach of the case-law of the Court in the matter.¹⁷⁵

The Court actually applied this on a breach committed by an administrative authority in *Larsy*.¹⁷⁶ The pragmatic approach of the Court, only seeking effectiveness of its case-law without claiming any hierarchy of Community courts, is well illustrated by Advocate General Léger stating that

[w]ithout entering into a debate relating to the nature of the authority with which the Court of Justice's rulings on interpretation are endowed, which a reply to the question raised does not warrant, I should make it clear that [INASTI's] liability (the administrative authority allegedly breaching Community law) will need to be evaluated in the light of the Court's judgment in *Brasserie du pêcheur and Factortame*. [... F]ailure on the part of a Member State or administrative authority to apply, to an identical situation, the approach taken by Community case-law constitutes a serious breach of Community law. The judgment in *Brasserie du pêcheur and Factortame* refers, in particular, to the existence of a preliminary ruling or settled case-law from which it is clear that the conduct in question constituted an infringement.¹⁷⁷

Thus when a national court has to decide a matter of Community law, it must follow the Court's case-law if it wants to avoid committing a “sufficiently serious breach”. It has binding legal force upon it.

¹⁷⁴ *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III*, supra note 30, para. 57.

¹⁷⁵ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 56.

¹⁷⁶ See supra p. 22-23.

¹⁷⁷ Opinion of AG Léger in *Larsy*, supra note 101, paras. 76-77, emphasis added.

It is true that “it is always possible to make a reference to the ECJ for a preliminary ruling on a question of Community law that has been previously raised”.¹⁷⁸ However, it will be the Court of Justice, not the national court who would change the applicable law (the precedent). Therefore we may not agree with Bengoetxea, who also contests binding force of the Court’s judgements. There is no way for a national court to change the interpretation of Community law enshrined in the Court’s judgment. It must either follow the rule of precedent or to refer the preliminary question to the Court of Justice only which may change it.

2.3 Köbler and *Commission v. Italy*: end of the “sincere cooperative relationship” or its preservation for the future?

When creating the System, the Court had to pay a price for it. Seeing the changes in the relationship between the Court of Justice and its national interlocutors, Joseph Weiler observed as early as in 1993:

In the past the European Court was always careful to present itself as *primus inter pares* and to maintain a zone of autonomy of national jurisdiction even at the price of non-uniformity of application of Community law. If the new line of cases represents a nuanced departure from that earlier ethos, the prize may be increased effectiveness, but the cost may be a potential tension in the critical relationship between the European Court and national courts.¹⁷⁹

It seems that Weiler’s prediction has turned into reality. Perhaps the most significant cost of the System lies in its tendency to undermine the relationship of sincere cooperation within the Community judiciary.

The Court of Justice must rely on its national counterparts in order to project Community law within national legal orders.¹⁸⁰ This is reflected by the Court itself, e.g. in its report for the IGC in

¹⁷⁸ Bengoetxea 1993 at 69.

¹⁷⁹ Weiler *J.H.H.* The least-dangerous branch: A retrospective and prospective of the European Court of Justice in the arena of political integration. In: Weiler *J.H.H.* The Constitution of Europe. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1999, 188-218 at p. 216. This chapter is based on Weiler’s article published in 1993 – Journey to an Unknown Destination: A Retrospective and Prospective of the European Court of Justice in the Arena of Political Integration. [1993] 31 J.C.M.S. 418.

¹⁸⁰ There is an immense literature on the role of national courts in establishing Community law in national legal orders. One of the most respected giving an overview from several (though not all) Member States is *Slaughter, A.M., Sweet A.S., Weiler J.H.H. (eds.) The European Court and National Courts – Doctrine and Jurisprudence.* Oxford, Hart Publishing, 1998.

Nice when discussing reform proposals on preliminary ruling procedure¹⁸¹ or in its own case-law.¹⁸² From the other side we may see the same approach from the German Constitutional Court - *Bundesverfassungsgericht* (BVerfG),¹⁸³ whatever its motivation.¹⁸⁴

The preliminary ruling procedure is the primary tool of this judicial cooperation. It was within the context of this procedure that the Court established fundamental constitutional principles of Community law – its direct effect,¹⁸⁵ supremacy,¹⁸⁶ protection of human rights¹⁸⁷ and the non-contractual liability of Member States¹⁸⁸ for their breaches of Community law to mention the most important of them.¹⁸⁹ That is why it is “justly regarded as the jewel in the crown of the ECJ’s jurisdiction”.¹⁹⁰ However, “the outstanding feature of [this] procedure is that it is entirely dependent on the goodwill of national courts”.¹⁹¹

This “inherent weakness of the preliminary ruling procedure”¹⁹² has on the other hand its own strengths. It forces the judges of the Court of Justice to have in mind how their rulings will be accepted in national courts (not only the one which has sent a question); it leads to an actual dialogue, instead of the simple issuance of orders to be fulfilled.

¹⁸¹ *The Future of the Judicial System of the European Union*, accessible on the web-site of the Court: <http://curia.eu.int/en/txts/intergov/index.htm> (13.4.2004) at p. 24.

¹⁸² For a cooperative relationship between the Court of Justice and national courts and its formulation in the Court’s judgements see e.g. Case 16/65 *Firma G. Schwarze v. Einfuhr- und Vorratsstelle für Getreide und Futtermittel* [1965] ECR 877 at p. 886, Case 244/80 *Pasquale Foglia v. Mariella Novello* [1981] ECR 3045, para. 20, Case C-83/91 *Wienand Meilicke v. ADV/ORG A. Meyer AG* [1992] ECR I-4871, para. 25, Case C-50/00P *Unión de Pequeños Agricultores v. Council of the European Union* [2002] ECR I-6677, para. 42 (based on Art. 10 EC).

¹⁸³ *Kooperationsverhältnis* (‘relationship of cooperation’) – cf. *Mayer F.C.* The European Constitution and the Courts - Adjudicating European constitutional law in a multilevel system. The Jean Monnet Program Working Papers 9/03, <http://www.jeanmonnetprogram.org/papers/03/030901-03.html> (11.1. 2004), at pp. 28-29. See also *Kokott J.* Report on Germany. In: Slaughter, Sweet, Weiler 1998, 77-131 at pp. 108-110.

¹⁸⁴ One may ask how “sincere” this cooperation may be when one considers that the *Kompetenz-kompetenz* debate was started by this court. The *Bundesverfassungsgericht* by formulating this relationship rather excluded any possible superiority of the Court of Justice.

¹⁸⁵ *Van Gend en loos*, supra note 17.

¹⁸⁶ Case 6/64 *Flaminio Costa v. E.N.E.L.* [1964] ECR 614 at p. 594.

¹⁸⁷ Supra note 18.

¹⁸⁸ *Francovich*, supra note 98.

¹⁸⁹ See further Anderson, Demetriou 2002 at pp. 26-27.

¹⁹⁰ Craig 2001 at p. 182.

¹⁹¹ *Mancini G.F.* The Constitutional Challenges Facing the European Court of Justice. in: *Mancini G.F.* Democracy and Constitutionalism in the European Union. Oxford/Portland Oregon, Hart Publishing, 2000 17-29 at p. 17.

¹⁹² *Ibid.*

Now, by allowing individuals to sue Member States for judicial breaches committed by the Court's partners to the dialogue, the whole idea of the cooperative relationship may be damaged. Indeed, we may read anger between the lines of the article, which has been quoted here several times.¹⁹³ This article was written by a member of the Netherlands Supreme Court (*Hoge Raad*), a court which is to be one of the interlocutors of the Court of Justice in establishing Community law in the Netherlands. He evaluates the judgement to be "mere token jurisprudence",¹⁹⁴ "a source of legal uncertainty, procedural entanglements and even more arrears in the decision of cases"¹⁹⁵ and then accuses the Court of infringing Community law at many instances under the heading "Those who live in glass houses should not throw stones".¹⁹⁶ It is probable that *Köbler* will not be welcomed in any of the supreme courts throughout the Community.

However, if we leave the idea of the Court's intentional creation of the System we are analysing here, we may also understand *Köbler* as a dogmatic consequence of the Court's previous case-law. We have seen that the Court held on several occasions before *Köbler* that it does not distinguish between different branches of the State authority and views the State as a single entity. It may be well that the Court did not have another option than to confirm its previous case-law on the matter. It was surprising that when applying (or one may also say misapplying) the test of sufficiently serious breach on the case of professor Köbler the Court was so benevolent to not find "sufficiently serious breach" in the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof's* not referring a question to the Court. It may be so because it did not really want to find this court liable.

Such an approach may be identified also in *Commission v. Italy*. The Court has found that Italian law in question was not in itself breaching Community law and that it was the construction and application of it by the administrative authorities and the courts which infringed the Treaty. However, the Court found the infringement in not amending the Law, which was insufficiently clear, not in the functioning of Italian judiciary (and administrative authorities). Thus the Court avoided condemning the Italian judiciary for the infringement.

¹⁹³ Wattel 2004. See supra notes 57, 60.

¹⁹⁴ *Ibid.*, at p. 182.

¹⁹⁵ *Ibid.*, at p. 179.

¹⁹⁶ *Ibid.*, at pp. 184-186.

The Court seems to be in a schizophrenic position: on one hand it is aware that national courts sometimes do not respect Community law and that it would be desirable to have means to force them to do so. On the other, the Court seeks to preserve the friendly relationship with these courts. Why is that?

It is well established that (especially lower) national courts are promoters of “the integration through law”.¹⁹⁷ It is not only so because they are the instances supposed to protect Community law on a national level. It is so because they are the ones which start the judicial dialogue. By posing preliminary questions they allow the Court to establish the doctrines necessary for the proper functioning of the Community legal order. Therefore, the Court of Justice cannot simply compel these courts to respect Community law. The Court must stay, in the eyes of national courts, as a partner, not a principal.

One must ask on the future of the judicial dialogue after the enlargement. It is questionable whether national courts in new Member States will follow their predecessors in promoting integration by active involvement in the debate. As a former member of the Court observed,

[t]he culture shock for judges and lawyers in the new member states will be definitely greater since many of them will have had little or no experience of legal methods which are second nature to judges and lawyers in the existing member states.¹⁹⁸

It may well be the case that the Court in *Köbler* and *Commission v. Italy* consciously opened a possibility to rap the new courts on the knuckles if they do not abide by the rules of the game.¹⁹⁹ The future will show whether the Court will open the doors widely in general and further change

¹⁹⁷ This is explained by the “empowerment” of the lower courts, allowing them to obviate their superior courts or giving them a power of judicial review, which they otherwise do not possess. Cf. *Alter K.* Explaining National Court Acceptance of European Court Jurisprudence: A Critical Evaluation of Theories of Legal Integration. In: Slaughter, Sweet, Weiler 1998, 227-252 at pp. 241-246.

¹⁹⁸ *Edward D.* Reform of Article 234 Procedure: The Limits of Possible. In: *O’Keeffe D. (ed.)* Judicial Review in European Union Law. *Liber Amicorum in Honour of Lord Slynn of Hadley*. The Hague/London/Boston, Kluwer Law International, 2000, 119-142 at p. 135.

¹⁹⁹ Cf. reflection on that in Czech: *Bobek M.* Odpovědnost členského státu za akty moci soudní; příspěvek Evropského soudního dvora k rozšíření Evropské unie? [Member States’ Liability for Judicial Breaches of Community Law – A Contribution of the European Court of Justice to the Enlargement?] *Časopis pro právní vědu a praxi* 4/2003, pp. 191-205. Another possible explanation may be also the reform of EC competition law implemented by Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2003 of 16 December 2002 on the implementation of the rules on competition laid down in Articles 81 and 82 of the Treaty, OJ 2003 L 1/1, shifting the enforcement to the national level and allowing national courts direct application of Art. 81 EC.

the relationship into a traditional hierarchy. It is submitted here that this change has not occurred yet and that the Court has done everything to preserve the cooperative relationship – something that can be illustrated by the benevolence shown to the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* in *Köbler* as well as by the Court’s attempt to avoid the targeting of the Italian judiciary in *Commission v. Italy*.

3 PROSPECTIVE OF THE SYSTEM’S FUNCTIONING

Having shown the existence of the System, the question of its prospective functioning shall now be discussed. Persuasiveness of the Court’s reasoning in the Founding Judgements and their subsequent acceptance by national courts will be analysed firstly. The problems of the System’s effectiveness resulting from the unmanageable Court’s case-load and procedural delays will be presented in turn. These problems may deter individuals from using the action of liability for a judicial breach and therefore threaten the System. This will be discussed last.

3.1 “We answer only what we want to answer, not what you asked...”

Throughout the presentation of the Founding Judgement we have seen that on several occasions the Court met difficulties when rebutting the arguments of Member States, which opposed creating the System (properly speaking, which opposed liability for judicial breaches or breaking the *res judicata* principle).

To mention the most obvious of them, the principle of *res judicata* is genuinely endangered, when an individual claims liability for a judicial decision. It follows not only from *Kühne & Heitz* that the original decision does not remain untouched if the applicant is allowed to seek its reopening before the administrative authority.

We may e.g. imagine a development consent given by a national administrative authority in breach of the environmental impact assessment (EIA) procedure. This procedure is prescribed by Directive 85/337/EEC (“the EIA Directive”) for certain categories of projects.²⁰⁰ Before the authority may give its consent, a study on impacts of the intended project must be carried on. If the authority fails to do so, the revocation or suspension of the consent already granted may be

²⁰⁰ Council Directive 85/337/EEC of 27 June 1985 on the assessment of the effect of certain public and private projects on the environment, OJ 1985 L 175/40. See further *Jans J.H.* European Environmental Law. 2nd Ed. Groningen, Europa Law Publishing, 2000 at pp. 321-328.

required, subject to the limits laid down by the principle of procedural autonomy of the Member States.²⁰¹ Moreover, the relevant articles of the EIA Directive are directly effective,²⁰² and a Member State is likewise required to make good any harm caused by the failure to carry out an environmental impact assessment.²⁰³

Applying ‘the Köbler Case scenario’ to the case of a possible breach of the EIA Directive, if the original consent is appealed in a national court and this court fails to refer a question or decides in breach of the EIA Directive (the latter possibility is probable, since in this field there is abundant case-law of the Court and many questions thereon may be considered as *actes claires*). The given consent may subsequently become *res judicata* and the developer may start to carry out the project. However, when a party (be it e.g. some environmental organization) may turn to the administrative authority and ask for re-opening the decision giving the consent, legal certainty of the developer may be seriously undermined, since the project may already be implemented. Examples when national courts ruled, contrary to the Court’s subsequent decision, that the relevant provisions of the Directive do not hold direct effect are known e.g. from the United Kingdom.²⁰⁴ Those decisions cannot probably be re-opened due to the long period from their issuance, however it is probable that similar decisions exist closer to present days and that their stability may therefore be undermined.

Thus when excluding the conflict with the principle of legal certainty or *res judicata*, the Court does not said the whole truth.

Moreover, on another place of the judgement in *Köbler*, to a certain extent the Court was contradicting itself when it defined the conditions of the liability and stated:

²⁰¹ Case C-201/02 *The Queen on the application of Delena Wells v. Secretary of State for Transport, Local Government and the Regions* [2004] 7.1.2004, not yet reported, para. 65.

²⁰² *Ibid.*, para. 61.

²⁰³ *Ibid.*, para. 66.

²⁰⁴ See e.g. *Kincardine and Deeside District Council v. Forestry Commissioners* [1993] Env.L.R. 151 or *Wychavon District Council v. Secretary of State for the Environment* [1994] Env. L.R. 239, both cited in *Bell S. Ball&Bell on Environmental Law*. 4th Ed. London, Blackstone Press, 1997 at pp. 281-283.

[...] regard must be had to the [...] legitimate requirements of *legal certainty*, as the Member States which submitted observations in this case have also contended.²⁰⁵

Contrary to its previous argumentation on the question of principle (i.e. whether a Member State may be liable for a judicial breaches), where the Court excluded any conflict with the principle of *res judicata*, here the Court is suddenly aware of the collision of principles, first, to make good any damage (or, protection of individuals or effectiveness of Community law) and second, of the legal certainty (and more particularly, though not expressly stated, *res judicata*). The rationality of such an approach is open to doubt. The Court would have enhanced the persuasiveness of its argumentation had it submitted to balancing argumentation, weighing the conflict of the principles.

As R. Alexy describes the balancing argumentation, “the greater the degree of non-satisfaction of, or detriment to, one right or principle, the greater must be the importance of satisfying the other”.²⁰⁶ When a court balances principles, it must firstly establish the degree of non-satisfaction of or detriment to the first principle (in our case it would be the principle of legal certainty). Subsequently, it defines the importance of the satisfaction of the competing principle (legal protection of individuals or effectiveness of Community law). Finally the court comes to a conclusion, giving reasons for favouring one of the principles.

In *Köbler*, the Court of Justice instead firstly excluded any possible conflict and then in another part of the judgement admitted that such a conflict exists. When dealing with the conflict, the Court only stated that there is another interest (legal certainty) which must be taken into account when establishing the seriousness of the breach, without any balancing the competing interests.

Another problem arises when the Court refers to the principle of national procedural autonomy. We may see that on several occasions the Court used this principle as a shield against troublesome questions posed by the national court. Perhaps the most significant example is the question on a competent court to determine liability actions invoked by judicial breaches. It is the main difficulty of the liability principle. The difficulty lies also in the fact that there is no

²⁰⁵ *Köbler*, supra note 9, para. 53, emphasis added.

²⁰⁶ Alexy R.. On Balancing and Subsumption. A Structural Comparison. [2003] 16 Ratio Juris 433 at p. 436.

guarantee that the court hearing the liability action will not make a mistake again – why to repeat the litigation instead of setting its final point, which would be the original, though unlawful, decision of the supreme court? Is not it better to accept that courts are human institutions as others and that they may make mistakes, which is due to their particular role (i.e. deciding in disputes) hard to remedy? The Court of Justice, without discussing all these considerations only referred to the principle of national procedural autonomy and stated that “[I]t is not for [it] to become involved in resolving questions of jurisdiction to which the classification of certain legal situations based on Community law may give rise in the national judicial system”.²⁰⁷

Moreover, the same problem may well arise before the Court of Justice itself: what if the Court of Justice breached Community law by its own decision? In *Bergaderm* the Court confirmed that “the conditions, under which the State may incur liability, cannot, *in the absence of particular justification*, differ from those governing the liability of the Community in like circumstances”.²⁰⁸ The Governments of Austria and the United Kingdom²⁰⁹ argued that holding a Member State responsible for a judicial act does not have its mirror possibility in the case of breaches committed by the Court of Justice, for the simple reason that there is not a court in which one may raise such a claim.

Commenting upon *Köbler* Peter Wattel even says that “those who live in glass houses should not throw stones” and gives several examples where in his view the Court of Justice itself breached Community law. He proposes to let the CFI decide thereon without a possibility of an appeal to the ECJ.²¹⁰ However, he proposes this only as an extreme example, since he pleads for exclusion of liability for judicial breaches.

It may be so, that the absence of the competent court on the Community level to hear actions for damages when the Court of Justice itself violates the Treaties, is “the particular justification” for different standards of liability on part of the Member States and the Community, mentioned in *Bergaderm*. However, Advocate General Léger rebutted the argument too simply: the liability in

²⁰⁷ *Köbler* supra note 9, para. 47, also referring to the Court’s previous “settled case-law” on that matter.

²⁰⁸ Case C-352/98 *Laboratoires pharmaceutiques Bergaderm SA and Jean-Jacques Goupil v. Commission* [2000] ECR I-5291, para. 41. See also *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III*, supra note 30, para. 42, emphasis added.

²⁰⁹ *Köbler* supra note 9, paras. 21 and 28.

²¹⁰ Wattel 2004 at pp. 184-186.

this case is excluded because the Court of Justice acts as the Supreme Court of the Community and its decisions cannot be reviewed by another court or tribunal.²¹¹ How can Member States accept this reasoning when the Court wants them to find a way how to make possible liability claims against their own supreme courts? Surely, it has its logic to let the Court of Justice decide in judicial breaches disputes. But when making such serious step towards establishing a kind of hierarchy amongst European courts, the Court should have reasoned more persuasively.

Sometimes it seems that the “judicial dialogue” is not a real dialogue but only the Court giving orders to national courts (“protect effectiveness of Community law”) regardless of the possible difficulties they may have in carrying out such orders (“it is not for us to resolve the problem”). However, the problem of breaking *res judicata* or designating the competent court to hear an action for the liability of another (not only necessarily the supreme) court is universal in nature and each legal order, in facing them, would necessary have to confront a contradiction between legality and the finality of disputes. Community law gives no weight to the importance of the rule infringed - it may be the improper classification of chicken legs (as in *Kühne & Heitz*) and still such a rule would claim primacy before conflicting national rule of a constitutional nature or a principle balancing the need for legality and finality of legal disputes. Unconditional principle of supremacy may then destroy that balance.

When the Court established the doctrine of direct effect and other principles enhancing effectiveness of Community law in the Member States, it simultaneously, to a certain degree, obliterated the distinction between the Community and national legal orders. It is submitted that it should have had in mind that Community law should not take precedence in *every* case, as the Court claims (arguing from the principle of supremacy). Having a uniform legal order also entails seeing its problems in their complexity, taking into account legal problems inherent in each legal system, not simply opting for the distinction whenever it conforms to the aim the Court is pursuing at the moment.

Having shown the problems of the Court of Justice’s reasoning, it is not to undermine the outcomes achieved, i.e. more efficiency and coherency for Community law. It is rather a case for

²¹¹ Opinion of AG Léger in *Köbler*, supra note 15, para. 94. He only admits such possibility in case of the CFI when the ECJ would decide thereon – para. 93 of the Opinion.

the Court's more persuasive reasoning, taking concerns of Member States and problems posed to their national legal orders more seriously. Otherwise the Court may, when promoting coherency of the Community legal order in a narrower sense (i.e. only on a Community level), create serious disturbances for national legal orders. We should have in mind that the multilevel system of the Community legal order is "composed of two complementary constitutional layers, the European and the national, which are closely interwoven and interdependent".²¹²

Arguments presented here suggest an approach, which may be called 'judicial deliberative supranationalism'.²¹³ According to it the Court would understand the Community legal order in the above-mentioned, wider sense, looking at the national legal orders as components not necessary on the inferior level of a hierarchy (the hierarchy which is denied by this approach). Concerns of national courts about this layer of the whole Community legal order would then be taken into account more seriously. The Court of Justice would have to base its reasoning not only on the "simple" principle of supremacy, but on rationality and coherency of its outcome with both layers – national and Community.

To conclude, the cornerstones of the System – the liability for judicial breaches and the possible breaches of the *res judicata* principle are necessary for making the Community legal order more coherent and effective. However, when the Court formulated these institutions it should have taken into account the problems it may pose to national legal orders and it should have given national courts more useful guidelines. The reference to the principles of Community law, like its supremacy or national procedural autonomy, may be damaging as regards the acceptance and prospective effectiveness of the Court's groundbreaking rulings.

3.2 The main System's problem: effectiveness and the Court's case-load

The main difficulty however lies in a prospective functioning of the System. It could be seriously threatened by overburdening the Court with "appeals" (i.e. requests for preliminary rulings in liability actions). Indeed, there is no filtering mechanism²¹⁴ preventing individuals to claim

²¹² *Pernice I.* Multilevel constitutionalism in the European Union. [2002] 27 E.L.Rev. 511 at 514.

²¹³ The concept of deliberative supranationalism is explained e.g. by *Joerges C.* 'Deliberative Supranationalism' – Two Defences. [2002] 8 E.L.J. 133.

²¹⁴ Apart from the limited possibilities based on the more recent case-law – see further Schermers, Waelbroeck 2001 at pp. 241-252, Lenaerts, Arts, Bray 1999 at pp. 39-44, Anderson, Demetriou 2002 at pp. 102-129. Critical appraisal

damages for judicial breaches in every case where they would be able to find a Community law point which was not given due consideration by the national court. Exactly the case-load of the Court through preliminary references is viewed as the most serious problem of this procedure and various solutions have been discussed on different levels without any of them being adopted.²¹⁵ It goes beyond the scope of this paper to analyse them in detail, however, one remark must be made in connection with *Köbler*. It was stated above that the Court failed to reformulate the *CILFIT* criteria, so that the obligation on the part of national courts' of last instance to refer preliminary questions are still defined in a very unrealistic manner.

It is also illustrated by the actual application of the test by highest national courts. For example, between 1.1. 1978²¹⁶ to 30.9. 2001 the *Conseil d'Etat* relied on the *acte clair* doctrine in 191 cases.²¹⁷ However, our inquiry need not be limited to this court (already criticised for its disobedience in *Cohn-Bendit*), as the German Constitutional Court - *Bundesverfassungsgericht* (BVerfG) may serve as another example. It held that a court's failure to refer a question of Community law to the Court of Justice may in some instances constitute a breach of the constitutional right to one's lawful judge.²¹⁸ It occurs when an ordinary court arbitrarily (*auf Wilkür beruhend*) fails to make a reference to the Court of Justice. The conditions of this

of the Court's limiting the admissibility to refer, especially when a national court does not provide the Court with sufficient factual and legal background, is *O'Keefe D. Is the Spirit of Article 177 under Attack? Preliminary References and Admissibility*. [1998] 23 E.L.Rev. 507.

²¹⁵ Cf. *The Future of the Judicial System of the European Union*, accessible on the web-site of the Court: <http://www.curia.eu.int/en/instit/txtdocfr/autrestxts/ave.pdf> (11.5.2004) at pp. 23-25, *Report by the Working Party on the Future of the European Communities' Court System*, accessible on the web-site of the Commission http://europa.eu.int/comm/dgs/legal_service/docs/du_e.pdf (11.5. 2004) at p 21. For a very detailed analysis of the proposed reform of the EC judicial system see *Turner C., Muñoz R. 'Revising the Judicial Architecture of the European Union'*. [1999-2000] 19 YB.E.L 1. For their discussion on limiting the case-load of the Court see pp. 63-68. We cannot expect that allowing the CFI to give preliminary rulings in certain cases will resolve the problem of the case-law of the Court. The same was expected as regards direct actions in 1990 when the CFI was established. E.g. in 1997 when describing the judicial system of the EC, it was said: "[t]he court seems to have reasonable case load, especially since the creation of the Court of First Instance". The situation now seems very different from this optimistic statement. *Barceló J.J. Precedent in European Community Law*. in: *MacCormick N., Summers R.S. (eds.) Interpreting Precedents. A Comparative Study*. Dartmouth, Ashgate, 1997, 407-436 at p. 410.

²¹⁶ Thus it applied the doctrine before its establishing by the Court of Justice.

²¹⁷ Cf. *Preliminary reference to the Court of Justice of the European Communities. General Report* (18th Colloquium of Associations of the Councils of State and Supreme Administrative Jurisdictions of the European Union, Helsinki, 20.-21.5. 2002), http://193.191.217.21/colloquia/2002/gen_report_en.pdf (29.11. 2003), at p. 29.

²¹⁸ *Solange II*, BVerfGE 73, 339 or *Kloppenburg-Beschluss*, BVerfGE 75, 223. I am relying on *Bobek M. Porušení povinnosti zahájit řízení o předběžné otázce dle článku 234 (3) SES [Violation of the duty to make a preliminary reference under Article 234 (3) EC Treaty]*. Prague, C.H. Beck, 2004, pp. 46-52. The cases of the *Bundesverfassungsgericht* are cited from this source.

arbitrariness are further specified by the BVerfG in another judgement.²¹⁹ What is interesting is that these conditions were formulated differently from those laid down by the Court of Justice in the *CILFIT* test. According to the BVerfG they are as follows:

- There must be a fundamental breach of the obligation to refer, which is in the situation when the court in question was in doubt when interpreting Community law,
- further the court intentionally diverged from the settled interpretation of the question by the Court and
- finally, there is no case-law of the Court or its case-law does not cover the matter in its entirety.

However, in its well-known *Maastricht Decision*,²²⁰ the BVerfG probably breached not only the *CILFIT* test, but also its own-formulated right to a lawful judge. This is so because when dealing with the interpretation of the Treaty (although formally interpreting the German Basic Law), the BVerfG referred no question to the Court of Justice. Instead of referring a question, it decided to hear the Director General of the Commission Legal Service.^{221,222}

Such practice of national supreme courts even led one member of the Court, when academically writing, to say that “the supreme courts of all [...] Member States simply ignored the obligation imposed by Article 177 [now Art. 234 EC] on at least one or two occasions”.²²³

The *CILFIT* test is even more unachievable for judges in the post-communistic countries to be fulfilled. They are faced with “post-modern deconstruction” of their legal orders,²²⁴ where a “legislative whirlwind” brings in its wake newer and newer laws they have to know and apply. It

²¹⁹ *Absatzfonds*, BVerfGE 82, 159.

²²⁰ *Maastricht*, BVerfGE 89, 155.

²²¹ Mayer 2003 at p. 7.

²²² The position of the BVerfG on the competences debate (Member States vs. the EU) is a probable explanation. The BVerfG would turn to the latter with a preliminary question only so as to send “its last warning” before it exercises its alleged ultimate *Kompetenz-Kompetenz*. Former Judge of the BVerfG D. Grimm even recommends German lower courts not to refer to the Court of Justice questions of competence but rather refer them to the BVerfG in order to allow the latter to express its strong warning itself. *Grimm D.* The European Court of Justice and National Courts: The German Constitutional Perspective after the Maastricht Decision. [1997] 3 Col. E.L.J. 229, at p. 241.

²²³ Mancini 2000 at p. 20. For an overview of instances where national supreme courts failed to refer preliminary questions correctly see Anderson, Demetriou 2002 at pp. 177-180.

²²⁴ *Holländer P.* Ústavněprávní argumentace [Constitutional Reasoning]. Prague, Linde, 2003, at pp. 11-23.

is not only due to the transition, but also because these countries had to implement an immense bulk of *acquis communautaire* to fulfil the conditions for membership in the EU. A prominent judge of the Czech constitutional Court, Pavel Holländer mentions the Czech Code of Civil Procedure, which had been substantially re-codified with effect from 1 January 2001. However, the amendments to this principal re-codification were reconsidered in spring of the same year and by summer 2002 it had been (also by indirect amendments) amended 18 times.²²⁵ In his view such a situation turns judges into “decision-making industrial plants” rather than rationally ruling bodies.

These judges will hardly have time to learn anything more than the very basics of Community law. This is also due to the fact that a lot of them were educated in times when Community law was unknown to law faculties. One cannot imagine such judges dealing with problematic questions of interpretation of Community law and applying all the requirements of the *CILFIT* test. It is excluded due to their limited language competence (which is a general problem of the *CILFIT* test – a judge knowing all 11 official languages – and in the future 20, should have spent all his life learning them and he would not have had time to study law as well).²²⁶ The requirement that the judge must be aware of the evolution of Community law at the date of its interpretation is also unrealistic, since, as mentioned above, judges in transition have difficulties in following the evolution of their own national orders only.

There are two possible scenarios for how matters will develop from here. The first is that judges in the new Member States, well aware of their duties resulting from Art. 234 EC and individuals’ right to claim damages for judicial breaches of Community law, will refer to the Court of Justice every question of Community law which arises before them. This will consequently afford the parties a very effective means of prolonging national proceedings, and the questions will emerge even more dependant on the will of the parties’ advocates and their knowledge of Community

²²⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 11.

²²⁶ For a methodology of such linguistic comparative exercise see *Van Calster G. The EU’s Tower of Babel – The Interpretation by the European Court of Justice of Equally Authentic Texts Drafted in more than one Official Language.* [1997] 17 YB.E.L. 363. She observes: “The characterization of all language versions of Treaty Articles and of secondary legislation as being ‘equally authentic’, places them in a relationship of interdependence. Rather than each bearing the authentic content of the text in question, they form that content together”. Indeed, not an easy task for a national judge to see the content of a relevant EC law before him.

law. The Court of Justice will be flooded by these questions, as a result of which the System it created will never work effectively.

The alternative scenario anticipates that the *CILFIT* test will be misapplied even more, further undermining the authority of the Court's decisions. National judges will only know that a *CILFIT* test exists, but since they see that it cannot function, none of them will really care about it. However, in this case individuals have their *Köbler* principle and may turn to their courts again, claiming liability. The unity of the Community legal order would be preserved, but the Court overburdened. That is why proposals for reformulating *CILFIT* were presented by academics²²⁷ and it was even heard from the Court. Advocate General Jacobs in *Wiener* asked himself

[w]hether it is appropriate - and especially whether it is still appropriate today, in view of developments which I shall mention below - for the Court to be asked to rule in every case where a question of interpretation of Community law may arise.²²⁸

However, he did not only propose the reformulation of the "language comparison" criterion (according to which a national judge must compare all language versions of Community law in question). The crucial point of his opinion lies in allowing for some filtration mechanism, whereby

[the *CILFIT* criteria] should apply only in cases where a reference is truly appropriate to achieve the objectives of Article 177 [now Art. 234 EC], namely *when there is a general question and where there is a genuine need for uniform interpretation*.²²⁹

The Court did not follow its advocate general (implicitly, in that it responded to the question posed by the referring court to the full extent). The Court passed up another opportunity to reformulate *CILFIT* in *Lyckeskog*,²³⁰ and *Köbler* is merely another instance of the Court's

²²⁷ *Rasmussen H. Remedying the Crumbling EC Judicial System*. [2000] 37 C.M.L.Rev. 1071 at pp. 1107-1110 and Bobek 2004 at pp. 125-128. For an opposing view, rejecting the need for a reform, see *Edward D. National Courts – the Powerhouse of Community Law*. [2002-2003] 5 Cambridge Yearbook of European Law Studies 1 at 7.

²²⁸ Opinion of AG Jacobs in Case C-338/95 *Wiener S.I. GmbH v. Hauptzollamt Emmerich* [1997] ECR I-6495, para. 10.

²²⁹ *Ibid.* para. 64. See also para. 50.

²³⁰ Case C-99/00 *Criminal proceedings against Kenny Roland Lyckeskog* [2002] ECR I-4839. In this case the Hovrätt för Västra Sverige (Court of Appeal for Western Sweden) invited the Court to reformulate the *CILFIT* test. The latter however did not consider the Hovrätt as a court of last instance and therefore did not have to answer the

aversion towards changing its position. Therefore, the Court, which claims the status of a constitutional court, remains unable to avoid the duty, as it had in *Kühne & Heitz* or in *Wiener*, to respond to questions concerning the tariff classification of chicken legs or nightdresses.²³¹ Probably no constitutional court in Europe has to resolve such questions. According to one commentator,

[i]t has been seen as curious that the European Court is expected to function both as the supreme constitutional court of a quasi-federal system and, at the same time, as the tribunal charged with interpreting Community law [...] however trivial or ill-thought-out the question.²³²

Discussions on the possibility of introducing a form of *certiorari* usually end by pointing out the special nature of the relationship between the Court of Justice and national courts, which would allegedly be endangered if the Court had the power to select questions.²³³

Another reason for the Court's resistance to limiting national courts' possibility to pose preliminary questions is that, as we have seen, the preliminary rulings are those which push forward the development of Community law. As a former judge of the Court T. Koopmans observed when discussing the *certiorari* option,

[i]t is not always easy to predict whether a certain case can ultimately contribute to the further growth of the Community legal. Judgements which, taken in isolation, may look somewhat innocuous, sometimes turn out to constitute the basis for a completely new chapter of the Court's case law. Under a *certiorari* system, there would be every possibility that cases of this kind would not, at first sight, look interesting enough to be taken by the Court.²³⁴

question thereon. Cf. however Opinion of Advocate General Tizzano in the case, paras. 60-76, ascertaining applicability of the test.

²³¹ This is a message of the whole collection of essays of the then advocate general and the judge of the Court G.F. Mancini - Democracy and Constitutionalism in the European Union. Oxford/Portland Oregon, Hart Publishing, 2000. For an argument denying the possibility of separating constitutional issues of Community law for a specialized constitutional court see *Kapteyn P.J.G.* The Court of Justice of the European Communities after the Year 2000. In: *Curtin D., Heukels T.* Institutional Dynamics of European Integration. Essays in Honour of Henry G. Schermers. Vol. II. Dordrecht/Boston/London, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1994, 135-152 at pp. 146-148.

²³² *Anderson D.* The Admissibility of Preliminary References. [1994] 14 YB.E.L. 179 at p. 180.

²³³ See Craig 2001 at pp. 197-200, discussing the working documents presented by the Court and the Working Group appointed by the Commission before the IGC in Nice 2000 (see also supra note 214). For another view cf. *Heffernan L.* The Community Courts Post-Nice: A European Certiorari Revisited. [2003] 52 I.C.L.Q. 907 at pp. 928-932.

²³⁴ *Koopmans T.* The Future of the Court of Justice of the European Communities. [1991] 11 YB.E.L. 15 at p. 30.

Thus, it is also the Court's concern to have a possibility to further develop Community law, which prevents the Court to take a further step in creating the Quasi-federal System by having certain filtering mechanism.

Such an approach consequently leads to an unmanageable volume of cases to be decided by the Court and as a consequence serious doubts can be put forth in regards to the functioning and *quality* of the System. As J. Weiler has pointed out,

[t]he issue of workload is not simply the delays which the heavy load on both Court and Tribunal create – justice delayed is justice denied. It is, and this is usually only whispered, an issue of quality of justice.²³⁵

Judges of the court rarely have enough time to deal properly with each case before them so that they rely more and more on their *référéndaires*. That is evident, if one takes into account the number of cases and the number of the judges.

The European Court of Human Rights has been very tolerant of the delays caused by preliminary rulings which extend procedures in national courts and therefore possibly breach the right to a fair and public hearing within a reasonable time. It ruled that the period of time of the preliminary rulings cannot be taken into consideration, since it would adversely affect the system instituted by Art. 234 EC and the system's purpose.²³⁶ However, although the Court in Strasbourg does not take into account delays caused by the Community Judiciary when determining breaches of the European Convention,²³⁷ an individual, seeing the time of the whole procedure, may be prevented from going to courts with a liability action and the function of this action as “an appeal” within the System will not work.

3.3 Individuals and the proper functioning of the System

The previous lines lead us to another question we should pose in relation to the System: does the “appellate procedure” really help individuals and consequently are they motivated to use the *Köbler* liability track to promote Community law within the Member States?

²³⁵ Weiler J.H.H. Epilogue: The Judicial Après Nice. In: de Búrca, Weiler 2001, 215-226 at p. 219.

²³⁶ Case *Pafitis and Others v. Greece*, judgement of 26.2. 1998, para. 95, available at <http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/Hudoc1doc2/HEJUD/199810/pafitis%20batj.doc> (12.5.2004).

²³⁷ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights, Council of Europe, Rome 4.11. 1950.

As we know, the liability of Member States is based on the need to protect individuals, who seek Community rights within the national legal orders.²³⁸ However, the time constraints may prove to be crucial when an individual decides whether or not to start such an action.

If we look closely at the whole “Fishermen’s tale”,²³⁹ i.e. the Factortame saga, we see that it took ten years of litigation to succeed with a Community-right-based claim in English courts. The story is well known to all Community lawyers, thus we will not deal with it in details. On 12 December 1988, the Factortame Company brought an action against the United Kingdom because of restrictive nationality requirements on registration of vessels.²⁴⁰ During the litigation, the Court had a chance to clarify important principles of Community law, like the impact of national procedures on the effectiveness of Community law²⁴¹ or the liability of a Member State for breaches of Community law itself.²⁴² The final decision of the Court of Appeal in the United Kingdom, awarding damages to the untiring applicant was issued almost precisely a decade later – on 8 April 1998.²⁴³

The same would probably apply for Mr. Köbler. His story began in 1996. It took two years from his request for the increment to the dismissal of his application by the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof*. We must bear in mind that in this case the proper preliminary ruling procedure was replaced by a simplified procedure whereby the Registrar of the Court asked in accordance with Art. 104 (3) of the Rules of Procedure²⁴⁴ whether the *Verwaltungsgerichtshof* deemed its question necessary. The latter withdrew the question, without waiting for the complete preliminary ruling, which generally takes approximately two years. Then the second claim comes – the one for liability. As we know the Court of Justice gave its rulings in late 2003 and we may wait for the decision of the *Landesgericht*, which, in line with the decision of the Court of Justice, will most probably

²³⁸ Cf. Harlow 1996 at pp. 210-215, critical to a “right-based liability”. For another possible base, i.e. the principle of subsidiarity see *Swaine E.T.* Subsidiarity and Self-Interest: Federalism at the European Court of Justice. [2000] 41 Harv. Int’l. L.J. 1.

²³⁹ See *Ward I.* A Critical Introduction to European Law. London, Lexis Nexis Butterworths, 2003 at pp. 123-129 with a description of the saga and its consequences for the UK legal order.

²⁴⁰ Case C-221/89 *The Queen v Secretary of State for Transport, ex parte Factortame Ltd and others* [1991] E.C.R. I-325. The action was raised against the decision of the secretary of State of Transport based on the Merchant Shipping Act 1988.

²⁴¹ *Factortame*, supra note 93.

²⁴² *Brasserie de Pêcheur/Factortame III*, supra note 30.

²⁴³ *The Queen v Secretary of State for Transport, ex parte Factortame Ltd and others* [1998] 3 C.M.L.R. 192 CA.

²⁴⁴ Rules of Procedure of the Court of Justice of the European Communities of 19 June 1991, OJ 1991 L 176/7.

dismiss the action of Mr. Köbler. However, making use of *Kühne & Heitz*, Mr. Köbler may turn to the administrative authority which took the original decision giving birth to his saga in 1996. And this time he should be successful, hopefully but not necessarily without further need to go to court. It would come as a big surprise if his story ends before the end of this decade.

This length of the Court's procedure leads to another problem: the structure of questions which reach the Court through preliminary references (or by the "appeals" as we call some of them in this paper). D. Chalmers witnesses this in his paper dedicated to the judicial politics of UK courts. The EC law litigation is used by strategic actors representing commercial interests or pressure groups aiming at the change of regulatory politics. We should not be deluded by the number of preliminary rulings given in the field of sex discrimination, which would tend us to think that discriminated individuals successfully used the EC law track to protect their rights. As D. Chalmers observes, "overwhelming majority of references are test cases brought against a private or public employer, but sponsored by the Equal Opportunities Commission or non-governmental organisations".²⁴⁵ Because the costs of a lengthy procedure and its uncertain result ordinary litigants do not risk the long way to justice and rather abstain from using all the possibilities given by the current system. If the System described in this paper seeks enhancing the unity and coherence of the Community legal order, the problem of the composition of the cases referred shows that it may achieve this end only in certain sectors, where these "strategic litigants" act. The Community legal order as a whole will not be affected substantively.

CONCLUSION

The Court's role is inherently difficult: it must ensure that when the Treaty is interpreted and applied, the Law is observed.²⁴⁶ However, it was not given necessary powers to ensure this objective *without* reading the Treaty with a great imagination, being subsequently accused that "[it] does sometimes judgements outside, or *contrary to*, the text of the Treaties".²⁴⁷ In 1990 Lord

²⁴⁵ *Chalmers D.* The Much Ado about Judicial Politics in the United Kingdom: A Statistical Analysis of Reported Decisions of United Kingdom Courts Invoking EU Law 1973-1998. The Jean Monnet Program Working Papers 1/2000, <http://www.jeanmonnetprogram.org/papers/00/000101.html> (18.5.2004) at p. 35. See also Dehousse 1998 at pp. 109-114.

²⁴⁶ See the discussion *supra* at p. 33.

²⁴⁷ *Hartley T.C.* The European Court, Judicial Objectivity and the Constitution of the European Union. [1996] 112 L.Q.R. 95 at p. 102, emphasis added.

Denning reformulated his famous dictum from *Bulmer v. Bollinger*²⁴⁸ on effects of Community law on domestic legal order stating:

No longer is European law an incoming tide flowing up the estuaries of England. It is now like a tidal wave bringing down our sea walls and flowing inland over our fields and houses – to the dismay of all.²⁴⁹

One should not be dismayed by Community law entering national legal orders; Lord Denning was quoted rather to show that Community law has become a part of national laws of all Member States and that the borders between these two systems have become more invisible than at the time of the Communities' establishment more than fifty years ago.²⁵⁰ It was also in that remote past when the Community judicial system was constructed by those who concluded the Treaties. It is obvious that this judicial system cannot fulfil the objectives of the Communities (or of the Union) of our days. Some problems were illustrated in this paper on the case of a “disobedient national court”, which still may prevent an individual to get his right stemming from the Treaty and create discordances within the legal order. Using Lord Denning's words, these courts still may build sea walls against Community law tidal waves.

The more structural problem lies in the Court's claimed position as the dominant (and almost only) arbiter of all questions of Community law. Without transferring more responsibility to national courts the Court of Justice cannot do its work properly since the case-load from 25 Member States' courts is simply unmanageable for the only institution. However, the Court itself refused to reconsider its position, having left the *CILFIT* test for preliminary questions admissibility in force and risking the raise of number of the preliminary rulings after the enlargement.

The paper described the ‘Quasi-federal Judicial System’, which seeks to remedy some of the most serious problems facing the Court. Thanks to the System the Court may control national

²⁴⁸ *Bulmer v. Bollinger* [1974] 2 All E.R. 1226 at p. 1231; also in [1974] 2 C.M.L.R. 91. Lord Denning then stated: “[The ECC] Treaty is like an incoming tide. It flows into the estuaries and up the rivers. It cannot be held back.”

²⁴⁹ *Denning A.T.* In: Introduction, to: *Smith G.* The European Court of justice. Judges and Policy makers. The Bruges Group, Occasional Papers, 1990, p. 7, cited in *Rasmussen H.* The European Court of Justice. Copenhagen, GadJura, 1998 at p. 373.

²⁵⁰ The establishment of the European Coal and Steel Community is taken into account here, since by the Treaty thereon the Court was founded.

courts' application of Community law and enforce its rulings and abidance by its case-law. Therefore notwithstanding the weaknesses of the Court's reasoning in the Founding Judgements, presented in the preceding part, the System should be welcomed as another step in the creating the coherent and uniform legal system of the Communities based on the Rule of Law.

It was mentioned in the beginning of the paper that its purpose was not to propose a new judicial architecture of the Communities. Building such architecture is not a proper task for the Court either. The new judicial architecture of the European Union should be designed by the Member States as those, who master the Treaties, or by people of Europe. However, this is another problem to analyse.

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